

CATALISI

Catalysation of institutional transformations
of Higher Education Institutions through
the adoption of acceleration services

D1.2 ACTING-LLS ACTION PLANS

29/02/2023

HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01

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ACTING-LLS ACTION PLANS

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CATALISI consortium			
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2	EY ADVISORY SPA	EY	ITALY
3	F6S NETWORK IRELAND LIMITED	F6S	IRELAND
4	EUROPEAN NETWORK OF LIVING LABS IVZW	ENoLL	BELGIUM
5	KAUNO TECHNOLOGIJOS UNIVERSITETAS	KTU	LITHUANIA
6	UNIVERSITAT JAUME I DE CASTELLON	UJI	SPAIN
7	LUISS LIBERA UNIVERSITA INTERNAZIONALE DEGLI STUDI SOCIALI GUIDO CARLI	LUISS	ITALY
8	UNIWERSYTET GDANSKI	UG	POLAND
9	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE CORK - NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, CORK	UCC	IRELAND
10	ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	AUTH	GREECE
11	STICHTING VUMC	VUMC	NETHERLANDS

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The primary objective of the CATALISI project is to assist seven European Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), referred to as 'Implementers,' in the successful implementation of a strategy and individual pathway for institutional transformation. The CATALISI Higher Education Institutions are located in seven European countries (as depicted in Figure 1): Greece (Aristotle University of Thessaloniki – AUTH), Lithuania (Kaunas University of Technology – KTU), Ireland (University College Cork – UCC), Poland (University of Gdańsk – UG), Spain (Jaume I University – UJI), Italy (Luiss Guido Carli University – LUISS), and the Netherlands (Amsterdam University Medical Center – AUMC).

FIGURE 1- CATALISI IMPLEMENTERS HEIS

The objective of driving institutional transformation within CATALISI is realized through the adoption of diverse acceleration services. Notably, the Living Lab service plays a crucial role in this endeavour, as it involves the establishment of CATALISI Acting Living Labs by the HEIs participating in the project. These Acting Living Labs serve as dynamic environments within the HEIs, where stakeholders collaborate to co-design and implement innovative solutions for institutional transformation. This deliverable offers insights into the outcomes of T1.3, focusing on the co-design of Action Plans for institutional transformation across CATALISI HEIs.

Following the Living lab methodology, the co-design of Action Plans began after an exploration stage focused on assessing local contexts, barriers, and framework conditions influencing institutional transformation across all CATALISI HEIs (D1.1). These Action Plans are closely tied to the needs and challenges identified during the exploration phase. They outline concrete activities aimed at achieving institutional transformation goals, along with key performance indicators (KPIs) and potential obstacles. Collaborative workshops involving implementers and their quadruple helix

stakeholders, representing academia, business, public administration, and civil society, were instrumental in developing these preliminary Action Plans. The workshops also enabled to narrow down and better define the priority intervention areas for each HEIs. The next phases involve implementing these plans and evaluating their effectiveness, with any necessary revisions being incorporated accordingly.

Adhering to the Living Lab methodology embraced by CATALISI, a mixed-method approach has been implemented, emphasizing participatory and iterative co-creation actions over desk-based research. The collaborative workshops were conducted by implementers between January and February 2024, significantly increasing engagement with external stakeholders compared to the exploration phase. In early December 2023, a preparatory meeting organized by ENoLL outlined the scope of the workshops and expected outcomes. This session aimed to establish a shared understanding, underlining the application of the Living Lab methodology and its key aspects. ENoLL also provided Implementers with a set of supporting materials necessary to (i) deliver the second round of workshops, (ii) report the outcomes of the workshops; and (iii) prepare the first drafts of the Action Plans. These materials included: workshop agenda template, Miro board template, session script, Action Plan template, registration form template, workshop feedback form template, ensuring that all Implementers could furnish the necessary elements. Subsequent bilateral meetings between ENoLL and all Implementers individually were organised to discuss practicalities associated with their workshops (e.g., adjust agendas to the specific needs of each Implementer, discuss the facilitation of discussions during the workshop, and adjust the relevant materials for the session).

The collaborative workshops led by the seven Implementers, applying the Living Lab methodology, drove HEIs to engage with their local stakeholders and collaboratively discuss their concrete activities to achieve the Institutional Transformation goals alongside with Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). The collaborative nature of these workshops led to achieving substantial outcomes which supported Implementers in developing the preliminary Action Plans for Institutional Transformation and are illustrated in this document.

The preliminary Action Plans developed by the seven CATALISI HEIs, in collaboration with their stakeholders, demonstrate a collective commitment to institutional transformation through innovation, collaboration, and excellence. While each plan targets specific intervention areas and goals, they collectively reveal common trends emphasizing data collection, training and skills development, communication, stakeholder engagement, co-creation, policy evolution, and alignment with global agendas. These plans reflect a dedication to fostering a supportive environment conducive to research excellence. As these plans are implemented, they signify a significant step towards achieving institutional transformation. However, at this stage they are drafted as a first version and will undergo comprehensive evaluation and review to enhance their effectiveness and efficiency.

Furthermore, the results of the co-design phase (Task 1.3) will also guide the update and alignment of transformational pathways developed within Task 3.2. "Design lab

for transformational pathway: strategy and agenda setting". The work done within Task 1.3 will also affect the activities with Task 1.4 "CATALISI Living Labs: Implementation stage" and Task 1.5 "CATALISI Living Labs: Evaluation stage" In addition to that, activities within Task 1.3 are strongly interconnected with WP4 on "Evaluation and Impact Assessment" since the initial Action Plans developed by all Implementers will affect the development of the CATALISI evaluation framework and will serve as a basis for assessing the progress of Implementers in achieving the Institutional Transformation goals.

The insights gained from applying the Living Lab methodology during the co-design phase of the CATALISI project will inform future trainings designed by ENOLL for CATALISI Implementers. While progress has been made, there is room for improvement, particularly in addressing challenges related to stakeholder engagement. Leveraging ENOLL's expertise in co-creation will be crucial for enhancing future activities. Moreover, continued co-creation will be essential for refining existing Action Plans and ensuring their alignment with stakeholder needs and interests.

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ABBREVIATIONS

CA	Consortium Agreement
CoP	Community of Practice
D	Deliverable
DC	Dissemination and Communication
DoA	Description of Action
ERC	European Research Council
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
HEI	High Education Institution
LL	Living Lab
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
MSCA	Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions
OS	Open Science
RCR	Responsible Conduct of Research
RI	Research Integrity
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
T	Task
WP	Work Package

1. INTRODUCTION

The CATALISI project aims to support Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in their journey towards institutional transformation through the adoption of tailored pathways and strategies, and the employment of acceleration services such as the Living Lab methods and approach. HEIs across the European Union (EU) have emerged as leaders in research and innovation. Strengthening collaborations with European Universities is essential for enhancing research impact and fostering institutional growth. Consequently, CATALISI aims to maximize the value and influence of research within universities' local ecosystems.

The CATALISI approach focuses on the three core areas (so called "Domains") for institutional transformation, namely: Research career and talent support, Open science and public engagement, and Sustainable research and education.

FIGURE 2 THREE MAIN CATALISI DOMAINS OF INTERVENTION AND RELATED INTERVENTION AREAS

These domains consist of various intervention areas and are complemented by seven targeted and innovative acceleration services: Living Labs, Design Lab for transformational pathways and counselling, Reinforced Human Capital, Predictive studies on skills anticipation, Marketplace, and Community of Practice (CoP). These services aim to facilitate and accelerate institutional transformations in Research and Innovation (R&I), reinforcing collaborations and alliances among European Universities, which serve as pillars of European values.

Within the CATALISI consortium, comprising eleven partners from eight European countries, seven universities, so called "Implementers," have committed to significant organizational transformations and are actively working to implement improvements in specific Intervention Areas, supported by four "Facilitators" (APRE, EY, ENoLL, F6S).

CATALISI Implementers, representing a diverse array of specializations and geographic locations, include Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) from seven European countries: Greece (Aristotle University of Thessaloniki), Lithuania (Kaunas University of Technology), Ireland (University College Cork), Poland (University of Gdańsk), Spain (Jaume I University), Italy (Luiss Guido Carli University), and the

Netherlands (Amsterdam University Medical Center), as depicted in Figure 3. Each university brings a unique profile and operates within distinct local contexts, influencing the scope and approach of their project activities.

FIGURE 3 CATALISI IMPLEMENTER HEIS

The **CATALISI methodology** is structured over four distinct and consecutive phases:

- The **exploration phase**, which focuses on exploring the local contexts, barriers and framework conditions affecting the institutional transformation of all HEIs.
- Subsequently, the **co-design phase** focuses on the creation of Action Plans for institutional transformation for all Implementers.
- The **implementation phase** is dedicated to putting the Action Plans into effect.
- The final **evaluation phase** is dedicated to assessing and validating the impact and the extent to which actions performed by HEIs were effective in achieving institutional transformations.

Figure 4 presents the key phases of the CATALISI methodology.

FIGURE 4 -CATALISI METHODOLOGY

Among the seven acceleration services provided by CATALISI Facilitators to support Implementers' institutional transformation, the "Living Lab" service developed within WP 1 'Acting-LL co-creation' plays a crucial role. This service aims at guiding and mentoring implementers on co-creation methodologies and competencies in line with the Living Lab methodology. This will enable the institutional transformation of HEIs (Acting-LLs) into user-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on a systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in real-life communities and settings. Moreover, the 'Living Lab' service supports all Implementers in elaborating targeted and effective Action Plans within the selected Intervention Areas. This happens through an integrative and iterative process for mutually valued outcomes that are the results of Implementers' co-creation with their relevant quadruple helix stakeholders.

After completing Task 1.1 "Setting-up the Acting Living Labs", WP1 initiated an exploration stage (Task 1.2) aimed at uncovering the unique challenges and needs specific to each Implementer's local context. This phase highlighted the diverse target intervention areas of CATALISI Implementers. The completion of Task 1.2 during the first year of the CATALISI project led to a comprehensive needs assessment involving Implementers and relevant stakeholders, laying the groundwork for the subsequent collaborative design of Action Plans for Institutional Transformation within Task 1.3. This methodological approach closely mirrors the Living Lab Methodology, ensuring that the solutions formulated—especially the Action Plans—are deeply rooted in the real-world challenges identified during WP1's exploration phase, thereby ensuring their relevance and alignment with current needs of CATALISI HEIs. Following the co-design of Action Plans, Implementers progress to the implementation phase under Task 1.4. Subsequently, the Action Plans undergo evaluation within Task 1.5 to refine them. This iterative process facilitates continuous improvement and adaptation,

ensuring the effective implementation of Action Plans throughout the project's duration.

This deliverable introduces the outcomes of the co-design stage within WP1, specifically within Task 1.3 'Co-designing Action Plans for institutional transformation.' This document presents the Action Plans formulated by each of the seven Implementers to address the identified challenges during the exploration stage, thereby shaping their respective institutional transformation journey. Following the establishment of goals for institutional transformation within prioritized intervention areas, seven collaborative workshops were organized by all Implementers to articulate and validate their Institutional Transformation goals, translate them into tangible activities, and define Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to monitor activity implementation performance. These workshops equipped Implementers with essential stakeholders' insights to develop comprehensive preliminary Action Plans.

This deliverable is further structured into the following chapters:

- **2. Methodology, Approach and Process:** This chapter provides details about the methodological approach employed to formulate Action Plans, spanning from defining the scope and tools to planning and conducting stakeholder workshops, culminating in the development of preliminary of Action Plans by all Implementers.
- **3. CATALISI Acting Living Labs Action Plans:** This chapter outlines the process of formulating the Action Plans for each CATALISI implementer, spanning from pre-identifying goals to the co-design phase through collaborative workshops, culminating in the development of preliminary Action Plans. A stakeholder participation analysis highlighting the quadruple helix stakeholders is also presented in this chapter.
- **4. Conclusions:** This chapter focuses on summarizing the results obtained from the analysis of the Action Plans presented in Chapter 3. Additionally, it outlines the subsequent steps to be undertaken for the implementation and evaluation of these Action Plans.

This deliverable is closely linked to other activities within WP 1, "Acting-LL co-creation," as the Action Plans provided will undergo implementation under Task 1.4, "CATALISI Living Labs: Implementation stage," and evaluation under Task 1.5, "CATALISI Living Labs: Evaluation stage." Additionally, its contributions extend to tasks within WP 3, "Design, Coaching, and Sustainability," notably Task 3.2, "Design lab for transformational pathway: strategy and agenda setting." This task focuses on tailoring transformational pathways to meet the specific institutional needs of CATALISI Implementers, which will be informed by the Action Plans formulated in this deliverable. Furthermore, this document is interconnected with activities within WP 4, "Evaluation and Impact Assessment." The input provided in D1.2, particularly the Key

Performance Indicators (KPIs), is essential for designing and developing the CATALISI evaluation framework.

2. METHODOLOGY, APPROACH AND PROCESS

Despite variances among CATALISI Implementers in geographic regions, specializations, and intervention areas, they embraced a **unified** and **harmonized** approach to collaboratively co-design Action Plans with stakeholders. This approach was centered around the **Living Lab methodology**, emphasizing **co-creation**, **multistakeholder engagement**, and **real-life context**.

FIGURE 5 KEY CHARACTERISTICS OF THE LIVING LAB METHODOLOGY

The co-design of Action Plans commences with Implementers pre-identifying goals under specific intervention areas which were further discussed during seven

stakeholder workshops organised by all Implementers with their respective stakeholders. More specifically, these workshops were dedicated to:

- (i) collaboratively defining the activities aimed at achieving the institutional transformation goals of all HEIs,
- (ii) identifying Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)
- (iii) identifying potential obstacles and challenges that can hinder the implementation of desired activities. The key outcomes of the discussions during workshops served as the foundation for formulating comprehensive Action Plans by Implementers.

The workshop sessions enabled a collaborative and inclusive environment, where participants outlined the activities necessary to achieve pre-identified goals for institutional transformation within specific intervention areas. These activities were then validated by the CATALISI HEIs and transformed into specific Action Plans.

Applying the **Living Lab participatory approach** and its key aspects such as **real-world focus** ensured that the developed Action Plans are not only theoretically sound but also applicable in real-life contexts of CATALISI Implementers, thereby enhancing the relevance and effectiveness of achieved outcomes.

Another crucial aspect in data collection was **stakeholder engagement**. The workshops actively involved diverse stakeholders representing the quadruple helix model — academia, industry, government, and civil society. In the second round of workshops, Implementers were encouraged to involve more external stakeholders. This inclusive and **multi-perspective dialogue** was essential for developing **holistic and sustainable solutions**, enabling the capture of a wide range of insights and experiences that contribute to more comprehensive and robust Action Plans.

All Implementers initiated the process with a standardized workshop scope, structure, and agenda, aiming to complete all key components of the Action Plans outlined by ENoLL in the Action Plan template. These Action Plans are directly related to the specific intervention areas prioritized by the CATALISI Implementers.

The Action Plan for each goal linked to a particular intervention area includes several key components essential for its implementation and assessment. These components consist of defining activities, specifying start and end dates, identifying the lead and contributors, establishing milestones, allocating resources, assessing risks along with mitigation measures, determining Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), and setting baseline and target values. Annex 1 presents the Action Plan template.

The co-design of Action Plans was structured into three main phases, covering the period from November 2023 to February 2024: (i) preparation phase, followed by (ii) data collection phase, and concluding with (iii) data analysis and validation phase.

The focus of each of the Action Plans development stages is described in the following sections.

2.1. PREPARATION PHASE

The preparation phase for the development of Action Plans and organizing the stakeholder workshops started in November 2023. ENoLL, being a leader of WP1, responsible for supporting Implementers in developing their Acting Living Lab activities, initiated the conceptual work dedicated to defining workshops' scope, objectives, methodology, expected outcomes, and a draft agenda. It also involved creating necessary materials that supported Implementers in delivering workshops and co-creating their Action Plans for Institutional Transformation.

A preparatory workshop facilitated by ENoLL on December 6, 2023 to review lessons learned from CATALISI's first round of workshops (organised June-August 2023) and set the ground for the second round of workshops scheduled between January and February 2024. A key focus was on introducing the methodology, emphasizing the application of Living Lab principles. This preparatory meeting clarified objectives and expected outcomes of the planned workshops, directly tying them to the development of Action Plans for the institutional transformation of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs).

Reflecting on lessons learned from the first round of workshops, several key insights emerged during this session. Implementers highlighted gaps and challenges, particularly in stakeholder engagement, data collection, and reporting. They provided valuable feedback, acknowledging the overall success of the first round of workshops while identifying areas for improvement, such as enhancing knowledge sharing and alignment among all CATALISI Implementers. A crucial takeaway emphasized the necessity of clear and concise communication for effective stakeholder involvement, ensuring a shared understanding of the project's goals. Additionally, the importance of more inclusive representation across all quadruple helix categories (academia, industry, government, and civil society) was underscored. The insights gained from these reflections played a pivotal role in refining the strategy and approach for the second round of workshops, with a specific focus on enhancing stakeholder engagement and communication.

During the preparatory meeting, also division of roles and responsibilities among partners was discussed. During the first round of workshops, ENoLL played a co-facilitator role alongside Implementers. During the second round of stakeholder workshops, facilitation responsibilities shifted entirely to the Implementers, recognizing that Implementers preferred sessions in their local languages when involving external stakeholders for a smoother exchange of insights.

Following the preparatory workshop, ENoLL shared all the necessary tools for the development of the second round of workshops with the Implementers. These tools, including templates for registration forms, a detailed scope and draft agenda, Miro boards for online sessions, and a session script template, were then discussed in detail during **bilateral meetings between ENoLL and all Implementers individually**. The aim of these meetings was to ensure alignment among Implementers, foster a thorough understanding of the tools and requirements, and address any queries in preparation for the upcoming sessions. Throughout the preparation phase, the ENoLL team maintained consistent support, readily available to assist Implementers before the workshops.

In preparation for the workshop and guided by the predefined scope and workshop structure, Implementers were tasked with setting goals and identifying intervention areas in alignment with the outcomes of T1.2 and transformational pathways. While ENoLL initially provided the agenda, each Implementer personalized it to integrate their unique goals and intervention areas.

Invitations and registration forms to local stakeholders have been sent out by the Implementers via email, offering relevant details in the respective local language. These details encompass the workshop agenda (Annex 2), personalized messages tailored to each workshop participants, and CATALISI factsheets (Annex 3). In addition to the formal invitations, Implementers capitalized on personal connections between HEI team members and stakeholders in their local ecosystems, employing diverse methods such as personal contacts, phone calls, and messages to secure the participation of relevant actors in the events.

2.2. DATA COLLECTION

The seven collaborative stakeholder workshops have been organized over almost two months, between January and mid-February 2024. Table 1 provides an overview of the CATALISI stakeholder workshops, outlining workshops' dates, modes, facilitation languages, and numbers of participants.

TABLE 1 OVERVIEW OF CATALISI STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOPS

HEI	Date	Mode	Language	Attendees	Quadruple Helix Representation
Kaunas University of Technology	08/01/2024	Online	Lithuanian	29	Academia, Government, Private Sector, Civil Society
Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	23/01/2024	Online	Greek	14	Academia, Government, Private Sector, Civil Society
University of Gdańsk	16/01/2024	Online	Polish	24	Academia, Government, Private Sector, Civil Society
Amsterdam University Medical Center	25/01/2024	Onsite	English/Dutch	15	Academia, Government, Private Sector, Civil Society
Jaume I University	22/01/2024	Online	Spanish	16	Academia, Government, Private Sector, Civil Society
Luiss Guido Carli University	16/02/2024	Online	Italian	19	Academia
University College Cork	12/02/2024	Online	English	17	Academia

Each workshop has been facilitated by the staff of each Implementer HEI.

Table 2 provides a complete overview of the organisers and facilitators in charge for each local workshop.

TABLE 2 OVERVIEW OF ORGANISERS AND FACILITATORS OF THE CATALISI STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOPS

HEI (Implementer)	Organisers & Facilitators
Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH)	Konstantina Tsimpita, Pavlina Lazaridou, Despoina Petsani

Kaunas University of Technology (KTU)	Eglė Butkevičienė, Aistė Balžekienė, Audronė Telešienė
University College Cork (UCC)	Martin Galvin, Ciara O'Halloran, David Hogan, David O'Connell
University of Gdańsk (UG)	Katarzyna Markiewicz, Sylwia Mrozowska, Sebastian Susmarski
Jaume I University (UJI)	Ramón A. Feenstra, Carlota Carretero García
Luiss Guido Carli University (LUISS)	Guido Miani, Anna Elisa D'Agostino
Amsterdam University Medical Center (AUMC)	Mariëtte van den Hoven, Miriam van Loon, Rita Alves dos Santos

Each CATALISI workshop was structured into two main segments: an introductory presentation and two collaborative brainstorming sessions. Annex 2 presents the workshop agenda template.

During this introductory phase, participants were provided with:

- A concise overview of the CATALISI project to ensure a shared understanding among workshop participants and clarify the purpose of their contribution to the initiative.
- Presentations by Implementers on the goals for institutional transformation at their respective universities, explaining the relevance of these goals in addressing challenges identified during the exploration phase.

After the introduction by organisers, workshop participants were invited to briefly introduce themselves, fostering interactions during group discussions. Then, participants, based on their expertise and interests, were divided into thematic groups that focused on the discussions dedicated to concrete institutional transformation goals. In these smaller thematic groups, two brainstorming sessions were organised.

- The first brainstorming session aimed to collaboratively define a set of concrete activities necessary to achieve the institutional transformation goals presented during the introductory phase of the workshop.
- The second brainstorming session was dedicated to developing Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) aligned with the activities defined during the first brainstorming session. Additionally, participants identified risks and obstacles associated with discussed activities.

This participatory approach was consistently implemented across all workshops, facilitated using common frames and templates guiding discussions and collecting stakeholders' inputs. For online participants, Miro boards were employed, while in-person participants engaged with flipcharts and posters. UJI opt for open discussions, prioritizing dialogue over Miro boards, based on the preferences of their stakeholders.

GROUP XX - [INSERT GOAL TITLE]				
ACTIVITIES TO ACHIEVE INSTITUTIONAL TRANSFORMATION GOALS				
Please indicate concrete activities that need to be completed to achieve desired goals toward the institutional transformation				

GROUP XX - [INSERT GOAL TITLE]								
ACTIVITIES		Key Performance Indicators				Risks & obstacles / Comments *		
Please validate activities from the first exercise and create a set of desired actions to achieve the institutional transformation goal(s)		Please indicate KPIs to assess the progress towards the identified activities				Please share any additional comments or suggestions regarding potential risks & obstacles		

The insights gathered from the brainstorming sessions and discussions were then incorporated into the Action Plans, along with other components such as the start and end date of each activity, milestones, resources allocation, and mitigation measures specifically addressing the risks identified by participants during the workshop sessions.

2.3. ANALYSIS AND VALIDATION PHASE

ANALYSIS PHASE

After the collaborative workshops, the analysis phase commenced to distill insights and outcomes from the discussions. Implementers diligently developed Action Plans based on the gathered workshop data, utilizing **the Action Plan template** to ensure consistency and completeness. Additionally, they completed **workshop report template** provided by ENoLL, detailing the workshop structure, methodology, participation, objectives, and main takeaways. This standardized approach facilitated efficient feedback processing, systematically incorporating essential components into each plan.

ENoLL conducted an analysis of all Action Plans shared by CATALISI implementers, as well as the workshop reports. This analysis focused on the co-design process, Action Plan activities, obstacles, and mitigation measures, aiming to identify common trends and obstacles in the formulation of the Action Plans. The goal was also to assess the co-design process and Action Plan development to identify any needs in terms of co-creation and co-design. Addressing identified gaps through further training and support would better enable the implementation of future activities within the Acting Living Labs of the CATALISI project.

As part of the analysis phase, during the CATALISI General Assembly in Castellon de la Plana on January 18, 2024, ENoLL and AUTH jointly facilitated a co-creative workshop among CATALISI Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). This session served as a platform for HEIs to identify and discuss primary challenges related to co-creation and stakeholder engagement in institutional transformation. Through engaging discussions, participants exchanged valuable insights and experiences, with the aim of developing effective best practices to overcome these challenges.

The outcomes of this workshop complemented insights from previous sessions, providing valuable information for refining future training sessions on co-design and co-creation for Implementers. The journey of co-creation remains an ongoing learning process throughout the CATALISI project, underscoring the importance for

ENoLL to consistently identify and address gaps while providing tailored tools and strategies to effectively meet evolving needs.

VALIDATION PHASE

After formulating the preliminary Action Plans, a crucial phase dedicated to validating the outcomes of the collaborative workshops will commence in the initial months of action plan implementation. This phase is vital for ensuring, on one hand, the accuracy and completeness of the insights gathered during the workshop sessions. On the other hand, it serves to provide valuable input for an informed evaluation led by WP4, which will lead to the review of the action plans scheduled for October 2024. This process complements the action plans by incorporating the user perspective, enriching the overall assessment

During this phase, stakeholders who actively participated in the workshops will be actively engaged to provide feedback on the outcomes and conclusions derived from the discussions. The primary objective is to confirm that the formulated action plans accurately reflect the collective input and expectations of all stakeholders involved.

The validation process serves multiple critical purposes. Firstly, it enables the identification and resolution of any discrepancies or omissions in the workshop outcomes. Furthermore, it reinforces the value of stakeholders' contributions by showcasing that their insights have been meticulously considered and integrated into the Action Plans.

To facilitate this process effectively, a **validation workshop results form**, provided by ENoLL, will be distributed by all CATALISI implementers to their stakeholders alongside the Action Plans. This form will comprise targeted questions specifically designed to gather feedback on the accuracy and completeness of the workshop outcomes, such as:

- *Were the identified priorities in the Action Plans reflective of the discussions held during the workshop?*
- *Are there any additional areas of concern or opportunities that were not adequately addressed in the Actions Plans?*
- *Do you find the proposed action items in the Action Plans feasible and achievable within the specified timeframe?*
- *How do you envision your role in contributing to the implementation of the Action Plans?*

The results of the validation process will also support the evaluation of action plans and help their revision, scheduled for October 2024.

3. CATALISI ACTING LIVING LABS ACTION PLANS

The Action Plans developed by the seven CATALISI HEIs, co-designed with their respective relevant stakeholders, illustrate a collective commitment to fostering innovation, collaboration, and excellence in pursuit of institutional transformation. While each plan delineates specific intervention areas and goals, collectively they reveal common trends, underscoring shared priorities and strategies aimed at advancing institutional objectives.

Implementers further refined and improved these plans through collaborative workshops, which served as crucial platforms for collaborative ideation and refinement. These workshops proved instrumental in better refining and narrowing down priority areas, involving quadruple helix stakeholders, equipping HEIs with co-creation skills and knowledge, and clearly defining Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and timeframes. They provided invaluable opportunities for stakeholders to collectively address gaps identified during the exploration phase, fostering a deeper understanding of institutional needs and aspirations.

After analyzing the CATALISI Action Plans, the following common trends have been identified:

- **Data collection:** Several CATALISI HEIs leverage surveys, interviews, and questionnaires in the Action Plan activities to collect insights, gather feedback, and assess current practices. This data-driven approach, acknowledged by implementers, facilitates informed decision-making, tailoring interventions to specific requirements, and engaging stakeholders in the institutional transformation journey.
- **Training and skills development activities:** Training and capacity-building activities feature prominently in the Action Plans, reflecting a shared recognition of the importance of developing essential skills and knowledge. From Research Integrity education to interdisciplinary collaboration workshops, HEIs invest in initiatives aimed at equipping their communities with the tools needed to thrive in today's dynamic research landscape.
- **Communication and stakeholder engagement:** Communication and stakeholder engagement are crucial components highlighted within the Action Plans, not merely as standalone activities such as dissemination or communication efforts, but also as vital strategies to mitigate potential risks stemming from lack of stakeholder engagement and interest. CATALISI HEIs aim to enhance awareness and foster a shared understanding. In line with this commitment, numerous Action Plans emphasize transparent communication, strategic stakeholder engagement, trust-building, and the cultivation of a shared vision for success.

- **Co-creation:** Co-creation has been prominently emphasized in the Action Plans, not only to enhance project visibility, but also to ensure that the implemented and proposed activities align with stakeholders' needs and insights. Workshops or focus groups for co-creation are frequently highlighted in the Action Plans as both activities and mitigation measures to ensure the effectiveness of initiatives.
- **Policy evolution and examination:** A consistent trend across the Action Plans is the emphasis on policy refinement and adaptation. Many CATALISI HEIs proceed with the initial step of revising and assessing current policies as a foundational strategy to build upon existing frameworks. Recognizing the pivotal role of policy frameworks in shaping research culture and institutional development, HEIs are committed to ensuring their policies are aligned with evolving needs and aspirations. By reviewing and updating existing policies or crafting new ones, HEIs aim to create supportive environments conducive to talent attraction, collaboration, and research excellence.
- **Alignment with global agendas:** Many Action Plans demonstrate a commitment to aligning institutional objectives with broader national or international agendas. By monitoring global trends and aligning policies with relevant frameworks, HEIs contribute to discussions on research accessibility, transparency, and impact. This alignment enhances the visibility and relevance of institutional efforts while fostering collaboration on a global scale.

As these Action Plans are put into action, they demonstrate commitment among Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) on their path towards institutional transformation. The Action Plans outlined in the following section are preliminary and will be subject to comprehensive evaluation and review in the coming months to boost their effectiveness and efficiency.

3.1 KTU ACTING LIVING LAB ACTION PLAN

3.1.1 Target Intervention Areas - Goals' Overview

Kaunas University of Technology has delineated and investigated 5 intervention areas (IAs) spanning three key domains: 'Human Capital', 'Research Modus Operandi', and 'Finance'.

Within the 'Human Capital' domain, three intervention areas have been identified: supporting talent circulation/mobility, accurately addressing lifelong learning, and strengthening of human capital. The 'Research Modus Operandi' domain encompasses an intervention area focused on public engagement with and outreach

to society to tackle social challenges. Additionally, within the 'Finance' domain, there is an intervention area aimed at promoting sustainability in research.

Based on the challenges and needs identified during the exploration phase under WP1, KTU has prioritized goals for each intervention area. These goals are in line with the university's medium and long-term vision.

The table below provides an overview of the goals associated with each intervention area.

Intervention Area	Goal	Goal description
Supporting talent circulation/mobility	Foster first-time international mobility of staff	To foster first - time international mobility of staff
Accurately addressing lifelong learning	Develop a non-formal education strategy for KTU alumni	To develop a non-formal education strategy for KTU alumni
Public engagement with and outreach to society to solve social challenges	Increase awareness of the academic staff about public engagement in research	To achieve the increase in awareness of the university academic and research staff and general public of the benefits of public engagement in research
Strengthening of human capital	Increase competencies of academic staff to publish in highly rated journals and books	To strengthen services that would help the university to increase competencies of academic staff to publish in highly rated journals and books
Sustainability in research	Strengthen interdisciplinary cooperation among KTU researchers	To strengthen interdisciplinary cooperation among KTU researchers

3.1.2 KTU stakeholder participation analysis

All participants from the first workshop were invited to the second workshop. The majority agreed to participate in co-designing action plans. Additional stakeholders, especially from external organizations based on the intervention areas, were identified to provide insights for the action plans. The aim was to achieve a better balance of stakeholders within the quadruple helix, including those at the regional and national levels, not just at Kaunas. The KTU team succeeded in attracting a larger number of external stakeholders for the second workshop.

In the end, **29 participants attended the collaborative workshop, distributed as follows: academia - 15, government - 6, civil society - 4, private sector - 4.**

KTU's intervention areas are primarily focused on internal actions. To ensure the co-creation and implementation of action plans within the HEI, it was necessary to include representatives from various centers and departments of KTU. Stakeholders from business and civil society were less motivated to participate in the first workshop, as they did not see how they could contribute. Consequently, the first workshop was dominated by academia. For the second workshop, the KTU team managed to secure greater involvement from external stakeholders by highlighting how their input could impact concrete intervention areas.

The table below provides an overview of the Quadruple Helix stakeholder representation in the KTU collaborative workshop on action plans co-design.

Quadruple Helix Sector	Organisation Name	Internal Department
Academia	KTU	Editor in Chief of journal "Studies about Languages", Faculty of Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities
Academia	KTU	DATA center, Faculty of Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities
Government	Lithuanian and Kaunas district political activist	Former Member of the Parliament, former Minister of Social Security and Labour
Academia	KTU	Writing clinic, Center of Foreign Languages, Faculty of Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities
Academia	KTU	Department of Human Resources Administration
Academia	KTU	Center for lifelong learning
Academia	KTU	International Relations and Study Programmes Committee, Faculty of Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities
Government	Kaunas City Municipality	Strategic planning, analysis and development programs division
Academia	KTU	Center for lifelong learning
Civil Society	Third age university	
Private sector	UAB 'SIMAKA'	
Private sector	UAB 'BITĖ LIETUVA'	

Government	Kėdainiai district municipality	Department of Public Health
Government	Kėdainiai district municipality	Department of Public Health
Government	Administration of Šilute district municipality	CB department
Academia	KTU	Document Management Office
Civil Society	Environmental Coalition	
Academia	KTU	Alumni center
Civil Society	Association of Kaunas Community Centres	
Private sector	Danske Bank	
Academia	KTU	Academic Centre, Faculty of Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities
Academia	KTU	LiDA data archive, Faculty of Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities
Government	Siauliai District Municipality Administration	
Academia	KTU	Academic Mobility and Networking Unit
Academia	KTU	Research Activity Analysis Office
Academia	KTU	Library
Civil Society	Institute of Future Society	
Academia	KTU	Academic Mobility and Networking Unit
Private sector	AGERSI	

3.1.3 KTU Action Plan Co-design

The KTU stakeholder workshop titled "Co-Designing Action Plans for Institutional Transformation," organized and facilitated by KTU aimed to collaboratively define concrete activities aimed at achieving the set goals, along with establishing Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to measure their successful implementation. Additionally, the workshop aimed to identify potential obstacles and risks associated with the implementation process. The event included presentations and validation of goals in the main session room, followed by in-depth discussions in separate breakout rooms. In total, six breakout rooms were organized, with one intervention area, 'Public

Engagement with and Outreach to Society to Solve Social Challenges,' featuring two sessions. These sessions delved into all five intervention areas where KTU plans to implement transformational changes and discussed the goals of these interventions. These outcomes provide the foundation for KTU to establish a comprehensive Action Plan.

The workshop has built upon the synergies within the quadruple helix and planned interventions will benefit from the intersectional and interdisciplinary knowledge provided by workshop participants.

Following the discussion on the first-time international mobility, follow-up actions were defined: to conduct a survey of pilot faculty to understand the reasons and obstacles for non-participation or low participation in international mobility; based on the survey results and in cooperation with different structural units at the university, to prepare a strategy how to encourage first-time international mobility at KTU.

The results of the discussion on the non-formal education programme for KTU alumni helped to identify priorities for action towards this goal. Based on these results four key actions have been identified: establishing an institutional working group; developing a survey for KTU alumni; developing a survey for bachelor's and master's students in their final year at KTU; drafting a brief that could serve for further enhancement of services in this intervention area.

The outcome of the discussions on strengthening services for academic writing in KTU has facilitated the identification of priorities to be undertaken in pursuit of this objective. All the suggestions centred around strengthening of the services provided by the Writing Clinic of the Centre for Foreign Languages, at the Faculty of Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities. As a result of the discussion, the KTU team was able to identify the following priority actions in this area of intervention: survey of Writing Clinic potential users; interviews with Writing Clinic users; announcing success stories or user testimonials in internal communication channels at KTU; develop Action Plan for strengthening of university-based services for academic writing.

The results of the discussion on increasing awareness of the academic staff about public engagement in research helped to crystalize several actions: first, additional trainings for researchers and public on citizen science methodologies, and second, development of a strategy or guidelines on how to effectively involve public into research.

In the intervention area for the sustainability of research, next actions are related to the organizing the networking events for two target groups within KTU: experienced researchers and PhD students. These events will stringent the potential for the interdisciplinary cooperation among the faculties, research groups and individual research. The needs and possibilities for interdisciplinary cooperation within KTU will be analysed in close co-operation with research related units, and the recommendations for strengthening interdisciplinary cooperation will be prepared and presented to the central administration and researchers.

Drawing from the insights gathered during the collaborative workshop, KTU has crafted comprehensive Action Plans for each of the identified goals. These Action Plans by KTU are detailed in Annex 4.

3.2 UJI ACTING LIVING LAB ACTION PLAN

3.2.1 UJI Target Intervention Areas - Goals' Overview

In the context of institutional transformation, UJI has identified several intervention areas, including research assessment, Open Access (OA), and citizen science. Within these areas, specific goals have been established, and they are detailed in the table below.

Intervention Area	Goal	Goal description
Research assessment and recognition of qualifications	Review of UJI's evaluation policies	Review of UJI's evaluation policies for their adaption to the new COARA inspired criteria promoted by the Spanish government
Open Access	Measure researchers' compliance with Open Access Policies	Creation of a scale of indicators to measure researchers' performance on Open Access. Also assess and improve UJI's OA journals performance
Open Access, Research Assessment, Citizen Science, Gender Equality	Creation of training materials	Creation of trainings materials for researchers to help them gain knowledge about Open Access, Citizen Science, Gender Equality in Research and Research Assessment

3.2.2 UJI stakeholder participation analysis

Invitations to the collaborative workshop were extended to internal stakeholders and external stakeholders connected to academia, some of whom also represented other QH categories such as civil society and business. This led to **the participation of 16 individuals** in the workshop.

The unequal presence of internal and external stakeholders in the workshop, with most being connected to academia, can be explained by the nature of the interventions UJI is trying to promote. During the first workshop, UJI realized that the topics of research assessment, open access, citizen science, and gender equality in research, along with the changes UJI wants to implement (e.g., reviewing UJI's calls for applications, promoting UJI's OA journals), are very specific to the university and difficult to replicate and understand outside academia. Bearing that in mind, UJI

aimed to gather stakeholders with an academic background who understand the needs of Spanish universities and have expertise in researching and implementing these transformations. Some of these stakeholders also had professional experience outside academia. This way, UJI was able to gather expertise and opinions from stakeholders who not only have an academic background and a deep knowledge of the Spanish university system, its legal framework, and bureaucratic demands (key to correctly implementing transformations), but who can also provide an external perspective and promote new ideas on managing certain aspects of the transformations to be implemented.

Some of the internal stakeholders belonged to three vice-rectorates: Vice-rectorate of Research, Vice-rectorate of Social Policies, and Vice-rectorate of Innovation and Scientific Outreach. These three vice-rectors and the Head of the Unit of Scientific Outreach and Citizen Science (part of the Vice-rectorate of Innovation and Scientific Dissemination) participated in the workshop.

Additionally, UJI involved some of its technical staff who work in the OCIT: UJI's Office for Cooperation in Research and Technological Development. These stakeholders are very relevant, as they will be the ones actually implementing most of the transformations, especially those related to research assessment, so their insights are crucial for preventing any bureaucratic and technical difficulties.

The table below provides an overview of the Quadruple Helix stakeholder representation in the UJI collaborative workshop on action plans co-design.

Quadruple Helix Sector	Organisation Name	Internal Department
Academia	UJI	Vice-rectorate of Research
Academia	UJI	Vice-rectorate of Social Responsibility, Inclusive policies and Equality
Academia	UJI	Vicerectorate of Research
Academia	UJI	Office for Cooperation in Research and Technological Development
Academia	UJI	Vicerectorate of Social Responsibility, Inclusive policies and Equality

Academia	UJI	Office for Cooperation in Research and Technological Development
Academia	UJI	Vicerectorate of Innovation and Scientific Outreach
Academia	UJI	Vicerectorate of Innovation and Scientific Outreach
Civil Society	Isonomia Foundation	
Academia	UJI	Office for Cooperation in Research and Technological Development
Academia	UJI	Office for Cooperation in Research and Technological Development
Academia and private sector	University of Granada and Cofunder of EC3Metrics	
Academia and Administration	Politecnic University of Valencia and National Agency for Quality Assessment and Accreditation of Spain	
Government	FECYT Foundation	
Academia and civil society	UNED and Knowledge and OA activist. Editor of BSPS Open and member of the Phil-Sci Archive	
Civil society	Young European Research Universities Network (YERUN)	

3.2.3 UJI Action Plan Co-Design

During the co-design process of Action Plans, UJI organized two separate workshops: the first involved internal stakeholders, including UJI's top management and technical experts with specialized knowledge in UJI intervention areas, while the second engaged a broader group of external stakeholders.

In both sessions, a group discussion methodology was employed, guided by questions aimed at assessing the feasibility of creating a scale of indicators to measure researchers' performance across various intervention areas, including gender equality, research assessment, Open Access (OA), and citizen science. Discussions also focused on identifying the human and financial resources required to establish and sustain this scale, along with determining specific questions pertinent to each intervention area.

Additionally, it was agreed to develop a pilot scale focusing initially on open science (OA) and later potentially expanding to include gender equality, research assessment, and citizen science, though ultimately, the decision was made to concentrate solely on OA initially. There was a suggestion to target research projects instead of individual researchers for assessment to ensure specificity, current relevance, and time-bound evaluation, particularly in the context of gender equality research. For OA and open science, utilizing indicators and data already collected by the library, supplemented by micro-level data provided by individual researchers, was deemed advisable.

The discussions held during the workshop played a crucial role in shaping UJI's approach to implementing changes across various intervention areas. By engaging both internal and external stakeholders, the workshop facilitated the refinement, alteration, or adaptation of previous Action Plans aimed at driving internal transformations at UJI. During the internal stakeholder session, emphasis was placed on enhancing the clarity and feasibility of institutional transformation objectives, with a strategic focus on incremental progress and addressing key issues such as research evaluation and open access. Additionally, the importance of training the academic community was underscored. The external stakeholder session provided valuable insights into technical aspects of planned changes, leading to a shift in approach towards measuring community adherence to open access policies rather than performance metrics. Moving forward, the next steps involve conducting a comprehensive analysis of current policies related to scientific evaluation, access, and open science, and exploring avenues for improvement and transformation. Despite the challenges posed by the complexity of these tasks and their potential impact on the academic community, there is optimism fuelled by the emergence of new national and international policies and initiatives aligning with the objectives of institutional transformation. This conducive context presents an opportunity to progress towards achieving these transformative goals.

After collecting valuable insights from the two workshops, UJI has formulated Action Plans for the three identified goals related to its institutional transformation. These Action Plans are detailed in Annex 5.

3.3. AUTH ACTING LIVING LAB ACTION PLAN

3.3.1 Target Intervention Areas - Goals' Overview

Aristotle University has established goals related to prioritized intervention areas as follows:

- **Research Assessment - Recognition of qualifications:** The focus is on providing certifications and accreditation to individuals involved in Living Labs and Citizen Science Projects, focusing on providing certifications and accreditation to researchers/participants in Living Labs and Citizen Science Projects.
- **Digitization of Higher Education Sector,** with a particular focus on promoting the usage of MOOCs, especially within the Medical School. This initiative is especially targeted at the Medical School, where the integration of MOOCs could offer significant benefits in terms of accessibility and flexibility in learning.
- **Mainstreaming of Open Science & Sustainability in Research** with an emphasis on facilitating Fair Data & IP Sharing. This includes facilitating fair sharing of data and intellectual property (IP) among researchers. By promoting transparency and collaboration, the goal is to foster a more sustainable and inclusive research environment.

During the exploration phase, Financial Sustainability for Research & Innovation Needs for Insurance of researchers & Stakeholders was initially identified as an intervention area for AUTH. However, after receiving feedback from stakeholders and external reviewers, it was deemed impractical due to its governmental nature and the challenges associated with effecting significant change within a two-year timeframe. As a result, this area was subsequently removed from consideration.

The identifies goals under each intervention area are outlined in the table below.

Intervention Area	Goal	Goal description
Research Assessment - Recognition of qualifications	Providing certifications and accreditation to LL and Citizen Science Participants	The focus is on providing certifications and accreditation to individuals involved in Living Labs and Citizen Science Projects, focusing on providing certifications and accreditation to researchers/participants in Living Labs and Citizen Science Projects.

Digitisation of Research	Integrating MOOCs Usage in the Medical Department	Focus on promoting the usage of MOOCs, especially within the Medical School. This initiative is especially targeted at the Medical School, where the integration of MOOCs could offer significant benefits in terms of accessibility and flexibility in learning.
Mainstreaming of Open Science & Sustainability in Research	Facilitating Fair Data & IP Sharing.	This includes facilitating fair sharing of data and intellectual property (IP) among researchers. By promoting transparency and collaboration, the goal is to foster a more sustainable and inclusive research environment.

3.3.2 AUTH stakeholder participation analysis

In the collaborative workshop conducted approximately six months after the first one, AUTH followed the same approach but aimed to enhance participation from the business and civil society sectors. To achieve this, the AUTH team expanded its outreach efforts, leveraging our existing network of stakeholders. Additionally, we emphasized the importance of spreading the word among the previously invited participants, encouraging them to nominate colleagues or peers who could offer valuable insights from these sectors.

In the collaborative workshop, **14 stakeholders participated**, representing the quadruple helix model: government (Municipality of Thessaloniki), academia (Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, University of Macedonia), industry (OKFN, Cyclopt, CERTH), and civil society (Open Knowledge Foundation Greece, ANTIGONE). The workshop also included representatives from key internal departments: the Medicine Department Laboratory of Digital Innovation, the IT Department, and the Technology Transfer Office (TTO). These selections were strategic, as the Medicine Department Lab of Digital Innovation provided insights into the role of digital tools in healthcare and research, the IT Department offered expertise on data sharing and intellectual property crucial for one of the workshop's interventions, and the Technology Transfer Office bridged the gap between academia and industry, contributing to discussions on collaboration and research commercialization.

Despite these efforts, the insufficient representation of the quadruple helix may be due to several factors. Limited external engagement, such as challenges related to availability and disinterest in theoretical discussions, may have hindered external stakeholder participation. Communication challenges, including articulating the benefits of external involvement and overcoming communication barriers, may have also played a role. Additionally, institutional culture, with prevailing norms or a historical emphasis on internal collaboration, might have deterred external engagement. By addressing these issues, future workshops can aim for a more balanced representation of the quadruple helix model.

The table below provides an overview of the Quadruple Helix stakeholder representation in the AUTH collaborative workshop on action plans co-design.

Quadruple Helix Sector	Organisation Name	Internal Department
Government	Municipality of Thessaloniki	Sustainability and Resilience
Academia	AUTH	IT Center
Business	Open Knowledge Foundation Greece (OKFN)	
Academia	AUTH	Medical Education Department
Business	OKFN	NA
Academia	AUTH	Technology Transfer Office
Business	Cyclopt	Software Development
Academia	AUTH	Legal Department
Academia	AUTH	Department of Studies
Academia	CERTH - The Centre for Research & Technology	Head of Technology Transfer Office
Academia	CERTH - The Centre for Research & Technology	Head of Technology Transfer Office
Academia	CERTH - The Centre for Research & Technology	Data analysis and modelling" laboratory
Civil Society	Web2Learn	Open Science and Training
Civil Society	ANTIGONE – Information and Documentation Centre on Racism, Ecology, Peace and Non-Violence'	Social Work
Academia	University of Macedonia	Librarian And Technology Transfer Office
Academia	University of Macedonia	Applied Informatics

3.3.3 AUTH Action Plan Co-Design

The collaborative workshop organized online by Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH) as part of the CATALISI project served as a collaborative platform for stakeholders from academia, industry, civil society, and policymaking to refine the university's Action Plan for 2024-2025. The workshop aimed to refine intervention areas, develop feasible strategies, and prioritize actions in line with the university's objectives. Key discussions focused on integrating Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), reviewing certification policies, and promoting open science and sustainability in research. Feedback from stakeholders and external reviewers led to the removal of a governmental intervention area deemed impractical, while another area was consolidated for efficiency.

During the collaborative workshop, informative presentations were delivered on each intervention area identified for the Action Plan. These presentations covered topics such as the integration of Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) into the university curriculum, the review of existing certification policies, and the mainstreaming of open science practices. Participants offered insights into the current landscape, challenges, and potential opportunities associated with each intervention area. Additionally, to streamline discussions and enhance effectiveness, the workshop consolidated the intervention areas of "Mainstreaming Open Science & Sustainability in Research" into a single focal area.

The workshop discussions brought to light several crucial insights regarding Aristotle University's Action Plan for 2024-2025. One notable focus was the need to review and enhance existing certification policies within the university, with collaboration from the Law Department considered essential to address legal gaps and ensure regulatory compliance. Additionally, challenges related to organizational culture and communication norms were recognized, underscoring the importance of standardized criteria for policy evaluation. The discussion also delved into the mainstreaming of open science and the facilitation of fair data and intellectual property (IP) sharing. Initiatives such as dedicated lectures and training sessions aimed to raise awareness among students and researchers about the benefits of open data sharing, despite identified challenges such as limited prior exposure and concerns about data misuse. Furthermore, the integration of MOOCs into the university curriculum, particularly within the Medical School, was explored for its potential to enhance learning experiences and provide flexibility for students, albeit with raised concerns about intellectual property issues and technical challenges. Overall, the workshop emphasized the significance of collaborative efforts in advancing research, education, and data sharing practices at Aristotle University. By prioritizing targeted interventions and establishing key performance indicators (KPIs),

the university aims to create a more sustainable and inclusive research environment, with comprehensive training and technical support essential for overcoming barriers and fostering a culture of open science and data sharing among researchers and students.

Having gathered valuable insights from the collaborative workshop, AUTH has devised Action Plans addressing the three identified goals pertaining to its institutional transformation. These Action Plans are elaborated upon in Annex 6.

3.4 LUISS ACTING LIVING LAB ACTION PLAN

3.4.1 Target Intervention Areas - Goals' Overview

LuiSS University has prioritized two intervention areas: mainstreaming open science and digitization of research, and public engagement with society to address social challenges. For each intervention area, the university has defined short-term, medium-term, and long-term goals. These goals are further detailed in the table below.

Intervention Area	Goal	Goal description
Supporting talent circulation/mobility	Short-Term: MSCA and ERC applications	Increased number of applications on research excellence projects such as MSCA and ERC
	Medium-Term: Improved LUISS' policies to attract ERC and MSCA talents	Improved LUISS' policies to attract ERC and MSCA talents
	Long-Term: Increased funds for research excellence projects	Increased LUISS' funds as a Host institution awarded for LUISS' projects of excellence in research especially at the European level (increased number of MSCA and ERC grants at LUISS)
Mainstreaming of open science and digitalization of research	Short-Term goal: Awareness about Open Science	Greater awareness about Open Science among the Faculty, the administrative staff, and on a governance level
	Medium-Term: Quality publications in Open Access	Increased number of quality publications in Open Access
	Long-Term: Adoption of Open Science practices	Increased adoption Open Science practices among the faculty

Public engagement with and outreach to society to solve social challenges	Short-Term: Awareness towards Third Mission	Increased internal and external awareness towards the Third Mission at LUISS
	Medium-Term: Quality of Third Mission activities and involvement of faculty	Enhanced quality of Third Mission activities done in LUISS with the active involvement of the Faculty with particular regard to public engagement activities
	Long-term: Role in the national and international debate on Third Mission	Enhanced role of LUISS in the national and international debate on Third Mission

3.4.2 LUISS stakeholder participation analysis

Invitations to the collaborative workshop were extended to a wide range of stakeholders. External stakeholders were identified by reviewing the records of all organizations and institutions that had been part of research projects in the previous few years, either as funders or partners. Conversely, internal stakeholders were identified among representatives of departments involved in the research process.

This approach led to **the participation of 19 individuals** in the collaborative workshop on action plans. External stakeholders from the government, private sector, and civil society were invited but did not participate. This may be due to two main reasons: first, the number of organizations and institutions invited was relatively small, reducing the likelihood of participation; second, the topics discussed, such as the mobility of researchers, were primarily of internal interest and may not have been relevant to external stakeholders.

The internal stakeholders included representatives from the faculty, who conduct research; representatives from the Research and Third Mission Office, who provide administrative support for funded research projects and public engagement activities; representatives from the library, who manage research archiving; and representatives from the Lectures and Seminars Office, who support research dissemination.

The table below provides an overview of the Quadruple Helix stakeholder representation in the LUISS collaborative workshop on action plans co-design.

Quadruple Helix Sector	Organisation Name	Internal Department
Academia	LUISS	Library
Academia	LUISS	Lectures and Seminars

Academia	LUISS	Lectures and Seminars
Academia	LUISS	Library
Academia	LUISS	Faculty
Academia	LUISS	Faculty
Academia	LUISS	Research and Third Mission
Academia	LUISS	Library
Academia	LUISS	Research and Third Mission
Academia	LUISS	Evaluation
Academia	LUISS	Research and Third Mission
Academia	LUISS	Research and Third Mission
Academia	LUISS	Research and Third Mission
Academia	LUISS	Research and Third Mission
Academia	LUISS	Research and Third Mission
Academia	LUISS	Law Department
Academia	LUISS	Research and Third Mission
Academia	LUISS	Research and Third Mission
Academia	LUISS	Faculty

3.4.1 LUISS Action Plan Co-Design

The predetermined goals underwent a collaborative workshop with stakeholders to discern the vital actions necessary for achieving each objective, along with corresponding Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to gauge progress. To facilitate discussions, the project team initially compiled a primary list of actions (and their associated KPIs). This preemptive step was taken due to time constraints. The identified actions served as a starting point, around which the discussion revolved, allowing for considerations of potential modifications and supplementary actions, as well as refinements to their respective KPIs.

Throughout the workshop, discussions on various actions and KPIs spurred engagement among stakeholders, with some topics generating robust conversations while others were met with consensus on the proposed drafts by the project team. Transitioning seamlessly between goals, key discussion points emerged, including the need for internal incentives to promote Open Access publication and strategies for hybrid publishing models. Participants also explored the role of incentives in fostering communication of research and public engagement activities, emphasizing the importance of incorporating Third Mission indicators into university strategies. Additionally, considerations were made regarding incentives to bolster application rates for prestigious grants like ERC and MSCA, including potential support from

external experts. Overall, stakeholders expressed general agreement with the identified KPIs designed to measure progress for each action, reflecting a shared commitment to advancing institutional transformation initiatives.

After gathering insights from the collaborative workshop, LUISS formulated Action Plans for each of the identified goals. These Action Plans are detailed in [Annex 7](#).

3.5 AUMC ACTING LIVING LAB ACTION PLAN

3.5.1 Target Intervention Areas - Goals' Overview

The Amsterdam UMC is focused on implementing an institutional transformation in two intervention areas: reform of research assessment & recognition of qualifications and research careers. Since these intervention areas are strongly intertwined in practice, UMC focuses on improving responsible conduct of research in general, by stimulating RCR through education, and stimulating a positive RC. This entails different actions, such as changing existing policies, and improving training and skills of researchers, staff and other target groups in the institutions.

The main goal is therefore to embed a learning pathway in RCR. To train researchers in relevant knowledge in research integrity, and improve their responsible conduct of research, different educational tools will be implemented in the organizations, resulting in the embedding of an RCR learning pathway. This RCR learning pathway and related educational activities, such as training, workshops and other engaging activities, will also contribute to the goal of stimulating a positive research culture in our institutions.

The goal identified within the prioritized intervention is outlined in the table below.

Intervention Area	Goal	Goal description
Reform of research assessment & recognition of qualifications and research career	Embedding RI education sustainably to increase RCR and research culture	Implementing various educational tools within our organization, culminating in the establishment of a robust RCR learning pathway. This pathway, accompanied by a spectrum of educational activities such as tailored training sessions, interactive workshops, and other engaging initiatives, serves not only to fortify individual competencies but also to foster a culture of positive research practices within our institutions

3.5.2 AUMC stakeholder participation analysis

A broad range of stakeholders was invited to the collaborative workshop on action plans, including policymakers from various organizations, RCR trainers, research integrity coordinators from different faculties, OS experts, researchers at different career levels, and potential students. Their expertise in research integrity, good scientific practices, training, and policy was highly valuable for the workshop's goals.

15 participants attended the workshop on action plans. The most relevant stakeholders were present either during the workshop or provided input in earlier meetings. Since the focus was on embedding policy and training, most stakeholders were from academia or government.

Representatives from different internal departments participated, including policymakers and researchers from various disciplines. Researchers with expertise in RI and RCR were selected based on their research in these areas. These researchers were primarily based at the VU Philosophy Department and the Department of Ethics, Law, and Humanities at Amsterdam UMC.

The table below provides an overview of the Quadruple Helix stakeholder representation in the AUMC collaborative workshop on action plans co-design.

Quadruple Helix Sector	Organisation Name	Internal Department
Academia	Amsterdam UMC	Senior researcher and teacher RI
Academia	Amsterdam UMC	Senior researcher and teacher RI
Civil Society	VU	PhD student
Government, Civil Society	Amsterdam UMC	Policy maker, RI confidential officer
Government	VU	OS training expert
Government	VU	OS expert, policy
Civil Society	Amsterdam UMC	PhD student
Civil Society, Business		NRIN coordinator
Academia	VU, Amsterdam UMC	Professor RCR, chair international RI networks
Government	VU	Policy maker research culture
Government	VU	Policy maker RI training

Academia	Amsterdam UMC	Senior researcher and teacher RCR
Academia	VU	Professor, chair ethics review committee, educational expert
Academia, Civic society	VU	RI coordinator
Civil society, academia	Amsterdam UMC	Research project support

3.5.3 AUMC Action Plan Co-Design

The defined goal underwent presentation and validation during a workshop organized and spearheaded by UMC with the objective of crafting a robust Action Plan to elevate the current RCR training provision at the VU and Amsterdam UMC. The workshop's focal points included discussions on the existing RCR training landscape at both institutions, pinpointing bottlenecks and improvement needs across diverse target groups, and outlining concrete actions to enhance the current training portfolio. Collaboratively prepared with central policy advisors on Research Integrity (RI), this workshop integrated insights gleaned from the Netwerk WI-Coordinate (NWIC) and previous CATALISI meetings. A wide array of stakeholders was engaged, ranging from policymakers from various organizations, RCR trainers, and Research Integrity coordinators from different faculties to Open Science (OS) experts, researchers of varying levels, and potential students. Leveraging the expertise of these stakeholders in research integrity, good scientific practices, training methodologies, and policy formulation was integral to achieving the workshop's objectives.

The discussion during the workshop led to the definition of activities aimed at achieving the goals. These activities include offering a network for exchanging training opportunities for PhD candidates, enhancing the quality of training and instructors, (re)designing and integrating training programs for undergraduate students and supervisors/senior staff, and establishing a comprehensive RCR learning pathway within the organization that aligns with evolving researcher assessment policies.

The RCR learning pathway is structured into three distinct target groups: 1) PhD students; 2) supervisors and senior researchers; and 3) other academic and non-academic staff. Throughout the workshop, dedicated group sessions were allocated to each target group, facilitating focused discussions on identifying concrete actions tailored to their specific needs.

Proposed actions included structural revisions to RCR curricula, discipline-specific training, and stakeholder engagement, with established key performance indicators (KPIs) ensuring effectiveness. Participants identified potential risks, such as limited reach and skepticism, and proposed mitigation strategies, including broad stakeholder involvement and clear policies. Efforts aimed to cultivate a culture of responsible research practices, emphasizing understanding individual requirements and integrating training into existing platforms while motivating supervisors through recognition and reward systems.

The workshop results have enabled UMC University to establish a comprehensive Action Plan for the identified goal, which is outlined in Annex 8.

3.6 UCC ACTING LIVING LAB ACTION PLAN

3.6.1 Target Intervention Areas - Goals' Overview

University College Cork (UCC) has chosen to address the intervention area of 'Sustainability of Research Finance'. This broad perspective acknowledges that financial sustainability issues are interconnected within the larger research ecosystem.

In the pursuit of formulating an Action Plan, UCC has pinpointed priority goals within the intervention area of 'Sustainability of Research Finance'. These goals are outlined and described in the table provided below.

Intervention Area	Goal	Goal description
Sustainability of Research Finance	Explore, identify and articulate financing issues for sustainability in research	This goal aims to provide strategic oversight to steer and integrate activities in the Action Plan, through phased development, across all goals and optimising opportunity for institutional transformation.
	Co-Creation Framework and Acceleration Services	This goal focuses on an integrated approach to the use of Acceleration Services and Co-Creation in support of the transformation pathway and Action Plan goals. Working across Goals 3-6 it aims to enable and support (i) internal/external stakeholder understanding of research financing sustainability issues; (ii) trans-disciplinary co-operation and (iii) co-creation of solutions to address the issues. Delivery of core co-creation activities is embedded in Goals 3-6; with additional actions identified here to support co-ordinate and integrated approach.
	Co-Create Revised Overhead Model (Indirect Costs)	This goal aims to revise the current research overhead model (indirect costs) and how research income is allocated. It contributes to a longer-term strategic ambition to realise an institutional research financing model that

		enables a positive research culture and that is reflective of the values of the institution. This research financing model considers sustainable and best practice overhead and research income allocation.
	Co-Create Engaged Research funding model	This goal aims to explore engaged research funding models, especially funding for smaller, grassroots community-oriented initiatives. It will co-design an ER model to pilot in UCC. It contributes to a longer-term strategic ambition to enable transformative relationships with society through the creation of institutional and societal-driven co-created agendas with new funding models.
	Co-Create and Pilot New Income Models	This goal aims to explore, co-create and test (pilot) new income models (e.g., Philanthropy etc.). It will co-design and pilot actions and initiatives that inform how the institutional can realise greater balance and diversification of research income. It contributes to a longer-term strategic ambition to realise an institutional research financing model that enables a positive research culture and that is reflective of the values of the institution.
	Co-create and Pilot Strategic Research Fund	This goal aims to explore, co-create and test (pilot) a new strategic research fund. The development of the fund will mobilise thinking to inform how we can better support and invest in capacity building initiatives. It will consider the wide range of issues and spaces within the research eco-system that would benefit from capacity building and devise and initiate a pilot strategic research fund to kick start capacity building mechanisms and initiatives. This will particularly include considerations around research talent, participation and performance for quality; research competencies for multi-, trans-, inter-, disciplinary cooperation; pipeline of career progression from undergrad, through PhD to early, mid, late career and succession planning; and continuity of knowledge + know-how between research projects.

	Research Culture: Communications	This goal aims to support all other goals, devising a clear plan and schedule for communications, dissemination and integrating acceleration services connected with each of the goals.
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3.6.2 UCC stakeholder participation analysis

The collaborative workshop on action plans invited a focused, targeted group of participants based on their expert and applied knowledge of the emerging action plan areas.

The workshop **included 17 participants**. Since the workshop focused on developing specific actions with a strong internal focus, it primarily targeted internal stakeholders with relevant expertise, while also critically engaging voices from national higher education policy. A select number of QH stakeholders known for their practical insights were also invited, although not all were able to attend.

Stakeholders were selected from key departments with influence and decision-making capacity in the context of the action plan areas. It was deemed critical that actions could only be proposed and developed with the support and contribution of these actors. Where key stakeholders were unable to attend the workshop, offline discussions have continued to build support for the CATALISI project and our action plan.

The table below provides an overview of the Quadruple Helix stakeholder representation in the UCC collaborative workshop on action plans co-design.

Quadruple Helix Sector	Organisation Name	Internal Department
Academia	UCC	RO College of Medicine & Health
Academia	UCC	Marine and Renewable Energy Institute
Academia	UCC	RM, College of Business and Law (COBL)
Academia	UCC	UCC Academy, Finance
Academia	UCC	Researcher, COBL
Academia	UCC	Senior Academic
Academia	UCC	UCC Innovation
Academia	UCC	Civic Engagement
Academia	UCC	Senior Academic

Academia	UCC	Institutional Data Manager
Academia	UCC	Director or Research Policy
Academia	UCC	Vice Head, CACSSS
Academia	UCC	Head of Research Culture, Engagement and Impact
Academia	UCC	Project Manager, UNIC European University

3.6.3 UCC Action Plan Co-Design

The identified goals were presented during two identical two-hour workshop sessions held online on Monday, February 12th, and Friday, February 16th, to accommodate participant availability and facilitate smaller group discussions.

The workshop had several key objectives, including fostering awareness, ownership, and support among stakeholders, facilitating brainstorming sessions for generating actionable ideas, validating and prioritizing goals, and utilizing stakeholder expertise to develop measurable, strategically aligned goals within institutional and national contexts.

Workshop discussions were facilitated using MIRO boards and were divided into two main discussions. The first discussion centered on brainstorming actions, with participants later voting on priority goals. The second discussion focused on considering implementation, reflecting on how to deliver measurable goals strategically aligned with institutional and national contexts, particularly in the short to medium term.

Working in small groups allowed for deeper and more focused discussions, with activities led by the CATALISI UCC TEAM, each drawing on their topic expertise.

Discussions highlighted the need for thorough exploration of identified topics at the goal level, indicating a shift towards concrete actions. Advancing these goals was seen as dependent on building awareness and engagement across various levels within the research community and beyond. The critical role of research culture in achieving objectives was emphasized, along with the need for additional information and data to inform decision-making. Concrete ideas for transformative and incremental actions were identified, underscoring the potential of the Action Plan to unlock innovative solutions.

The discussions also emphasized the Action Plan's role in mobilizing internal change, contributing to national advocacy and policy, and fostering societal impact. Leveraging international experiences and partnerships was seen as crucial, as was embedding CATALISI within institutional and national platforms to sustain stakeholder engagement and inform policy dialogue effectively.

Insights from the collaborative workshops have allowed UCC to formulate actions plans for each of the identified goals. They are outlined in Annex 9.

3.7. UG ACTING LIVING LAB ACTION PLAN

3.7.1 Target Intervention Areas - Goals' Overview

UG University has prioritized two intervention areas: "Public engagement with and outreach to society to solve social challenges" and "Sustainability in campus operation." Goals under these intervention areas have been identified by UG and are outlined and described in the table below.

Intervention Area	Goal	Goal description
Public engagement with and outreach to society to solve social challenges	Establishment of a Strategic Team for seaports	Creation of smaller working groups to carry out thematically directed work for the benefit of business, in this case ports
	Preparation of dedicated bachelor's and master's theses for business	Going out to meet the needs of business, preparing "commissioned" dissertations that will have a use in the socio-economic environment
Sustainability in campus operation	Week of current knowledge	Reduction of paper waste in the economic department (pilot action; at least one action)
	ECOthon - close the loop	Involvement of the student community in the sustainable operations of the University of Gdansk campus. Encourage students - through the competition between the Faculty of Economics and the Faculty of Management - to care about the health of the planet (the secondary circulation of things) and their own (short-distance run between both Faculties). An off-road run where the 'entry fee' is to donate an item for recycling (e.g., an old phone) or for further circulation (e.g. clothing).

3.7.2 UG stakeholder participation analysis

UG CATALISI project team focuses, in their institutional transformation journey, on research, finance, and human capital. The UG CATALISI team conducted an extensive stakeholder mapping and invited a diverse group of participants to the collaborative workshop on action plans, ensuring alignment with the workshop's agenda.

Consequently, **24 individuals participated**, representing the 4 categories of the quadruple helix.

Essential stakeholders for achieving the institutional transformation goals included relevant internal departments and external stakeholders representing the civil society and the government categories. Their presence and insights significantly enriched the workshop discussions.

The table below provides an overview of the Quadruple Helix stakeholder representation in the UG collaborative workshop on action plans co-design

Quadruple Helix Sector	Organisation Name	Internal Department
Academia	University of Gdańsk	Specialist of administration
Government	Warsaw Modlin Airport Ltd.	Acting CEO
Academia	University of Gdańsk	researcher and teacher
Academia	University of Gdansk	Project Manager Catalisi
Private Sector	Port of Gdynia Authority SA	Head of Department
Government	Starostwo Powiatowe w Pucku	Wicestarosta
Civil society	Gdańska Fundacja Przedsiębiorczości	Start-up Development Specialist
Academia	Uniwersytet Gdański	vice-dean research and int. cooperation
Civil Society	Gdańska Fundacja Przedsiębiorczości/Inkubator Starter (Gdansk Entrepreneurship Foundation/Incubator Starter)	Specialist in Entrepreneurial Education
Academia	University od Gdańsk	Project manager, centre for sustainable development
Academia	University of Gdansk	Vice -Rector for Cooperation and Development
Academia	University of Gdańsk	project manager - Centre for Sustainable Development
Academia	Uniwersytet Gdański	Koordinator
Academia	Uniwersytet Gdański	Assistant Professor

Academia	University of Gdansk	Professor
Academia	University of Gdańsk	administration officer
Civil Society	Incubator STARTER	Start-up Development Specialist
Government	Gdansk Economic Development Foundation and InvestGDA	Chairman of the Board of Gdansk Economic Development Foundation Andrzej Deputy Manager of InvestGDA
Government	Gdansk Economic Development Foundation and InvestGDA	Chairman of the Council of Gdansk Economic Development Foundation and Deputy Manager of INVESTGDA
Academia	University of Gdańsk	director of Technology Transfer Office
Academia	Uniwersytet Gdański	Director
Academia	University of Gdansk	Support in connecting the UG with busieness
Academia	University of Gdansk	Academic Teacher
Civil Society	European Network of Living Labs	Project Manager

3.7.3 UG Action Plan co-design

The University of Gdansk orchestrated a collaborative workshop with the explicit aim of co-designing Action Plans tailored to identified goals. Serving as a dynamic platform, the workshop facilitated exploration of collaborative opportunities and dialogue among diverse stakeholders, all with a shared focus on enhancing service revenues. Aligned seamlessly with the intervention areas delineated in the CATALISI project—namely, Public engagement with and outreach to society to solve social challenges, and Sustainability in campus operations—the workshop delved deeply into specific objectives. These objectives spanned a spectrum, from discussions on tools for financing joint projects in research and development (R&D) to exploring potential avenues for cooperation in Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Moreover, the agenda encompassed surveying business expectations from universities and piloting a tailored questionnaire designed to serve as a tool for business surveys. Through these meticulously outlined objectives, the workshop fostered an environment conducive to cultivating meaningful partnerships, driving innovation, and collectively addressing pressing societal challenges, all while ensuring sustainability in campus operations.

The discussions that ensued during the workshops underscored the vital necessity of creating tools for conducting surveys within departments, with a sharp focus on unlocking the potential of researchers to extend services to the external environment. This emphasis was augmented by a concerted effort to facilitate knowledge exchange and address pervasive barriers, particularly those relating to

communication and time constraints. Furthermore, concerted efforts were made to enhance the visibility of services to external entities, underscored by strategic initiatives such as optimizing contact points between the university and businesses, establishing specialized teams, and tailoring services to cater to the needs of aspiring entrepreneurs. Notably, plans were set in motion to develop a robust tool for studying business needs via online surveys, signaling a commitment to fostering effective dialogue and responsiveness to industry demands. Additionally, the discourse embraced initiatives aimed at heightening awareness of non-financial reporting and advancing sustainable development within the university community, with proposals ranging from postgraduate studies to ESG non-financial reporting training. Finally, the workshops outlined a roadmap for fostering collaboration in research and education, championing joint projects between scientists and businesses, as well as forging alliances with students through dedicated theses—an endeavor aimed at nurturing a vibrant culture of innovation and knowledge exchange within the university ecosystem.

The insights gleaned from these discussions have enabled UG to craft Action Plans tailored to the identified goals, which are detailed in Annex 10.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The collaborative journey undertaken by CATALISI Implementers is ongoing, involving seven Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) across Europe. Each institution is committed to driving institutional transformation by implementing tailored actions within specific intervention areas, while also considering their individual needs and contexts.

After identifying the needs and challenges for institutional transformation during the exploration stage, CATALISI Implementers moved on to develop Action Plans. This process included defining goals related to institutional transformation and working with stakeholders from the quadruple helix to co-design Action Plans in collaborative workshops. Based on the outcomes of these workshops, the CATALISI implementers formulated preliminary Action Plans. They fostered deeper engagement with external stakeholders and enhanced the application of the Living Lab methodology.

The Action Plans developed collaboratively by the seven CATALISI HEIs and their stakeholders illustrate a unified commitment towards fostering innovation, collaboration, and excellence in advancing institutional transformation. While each plan addresses specific intervention areas and goals, collectively they reveal overarching themes that underscore shared priorities and strategies. These themes include a strong emphasis on data-driven approaches, with HEIs utilizing surveys, interviews, and questionnaires to gather insights for informed decision-making and tailored interventions. Additionally, there is a notable focus on training and skills development initiatives, reflecting a recognition of the importance of equipping

communities with essential skills and knowledge, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration, and upholding research integrity.

Communication and stakeholder engagement emerge as critical components within the Action Plans, serving not only as standalone activities but also as vital strategies to mitigate potential risks with the Action Plans implementation and to foster a shared vision for success. HEIs prioritize transparent communication, strategic stakeholder engagement, and trust-building to enhance awareness and ensure active participation in the institutional transformation journey.

Furthermore, co-creation is prominently emphasized across the Action Plans, highlighting a commitment to aligning activities with stakeholders' needs and insights through workshops and focus groups.

Regarding the next steps for the Action Plans, they have entered an initial implementation phase until September 2024. Continuous evaluation will take place during this period, with active engagement from stakeholders. Subsequently, a review will be conducted at the end of the initial implementation phase, followed by the commencement of the second phase of implementation.

In terms of **organizational considerations**, specific challenges and areas for improvement have been pinpointed, along with recommendations regarding co-creation. These insights were shared during a workshop led by ENOLL and AUTH as part of the CATALISI general assembly on January 18, 2024. The focal points primarily revolve around the following key areas:

- **Importance of stakeholder identification and analysis:** Successful stakeholder engagement begins with accurately defining and identifying stakeholders. Internal preparation is essential not only for identifying the appropriate stakeholders but also for analysing and understanding them. This enables the adoption of effective communication strategies tailored to their interests and roles. It is crucial to find a common language and understanding with stakeholders about institutional transformation, emphasizing the importance of communication in the process.
- **Time and resource constraints:** A significant challenge identified is the amount of time required for the stakeholder engagement/co-creation process, particularly in terms of preparation and keeping stakeholders updated. This raises concerns about certain HEIs lacking the necessary resources dedicated to stakeholder engagement due to competing activities.
- **Citizen and civil society engagement:** Engaging citizens and civil society poses a major challenge in the co-creation process for many HEIs. To address this, it is essential to create opportunities for meaningful involvement and dialogue with these stakeholders, fostering a sense of ownership and collaboration in the transformation process.

- **Accessibility of external stakeholders to universities:** The accessibility of external stakeholders to universities is identified as a challenge. To overcome this, it is important to organize focus groups based on topics and expertise of stakeholders. Technical topics may be inaccessible to some stakeholders, potentially leading to a loss of interest in the overall process. These focus groups can facilitate engagement and ensure that discussions are tailored to stakeholders' needs and interests.

The insights garnered from the collaborative workshops, along with the lessons learned and challenges encountered in co-creation, will be instrumental in shaping future training sessions developed by ENoLL for CATALISI Implementers. While the adoption of the Living Lab approach has advanced and improved, there are still areas primed for refinement.

The CATALISI project presents an ideal opportunity for Implementers to leverage ENoLL's expertise in co-creation, thereby enhancing their pursuit of forthcoming activities. Additionally, it's crucial to underscore that co-creation will be indispensable for various critical endeavours within CATALISI, including the evaluation and enhancement of existing Action Plans post the initial phase of implementation.

ANNEX 1 – ACTION PLAN TEMPLATE

Goal title												
Intervention area		Leader										
Start		End										
Goal description												
No.	Activity	Leader	Contributors	Start date	End date	Milestones	Resources	Risks and obstacles	Mitigation measures	KPIs	Baseline value	Target value
1												
2												
3												
4												
5												

ANNEX 2 – WORKSHOP AGENDA TEMPLATE

CATALISI WORKSHOP

Co-Designing Action Plans for Institutional Transformation

[[INSERT HEI NAME]]

[[INSERT WORKSHOP DATE AND TIME]]

[[INSERT MEETING DETAILS, LINK TO AN ONLINE MEETING]]

Agenda Point	Time
Welcome and Introduction to the Workshop	10:00 - 10:05
Introduction to the CATALISI Project and Goals for the Institutional Transformation	10:05 - 10:25
Tour de Table	10:25 - 10:35
Activities for Achieving Institutional Transformation Goals	10:35 - 11:35
Coffee Break	11:35 - 11:45
KPIs Formulation and Alignment	11:45 - 12:50
Summary and Next Steps	12:50 - 13:00

ANNEX 3 – CATALISI FACTSHEET

The CATALISI project

CATALISI is an EU-funded project that will help and support Higher Education Institutions to successfully implement a strategy and individual pathway for institutional transformation through the adoption of acceleration services.

CATALISI will analyse how the governance of Higher Education Institutions can be changed, considering the governance as a way in which societal and state actors interact in order to transform Science Technology and Innovation systems, by regulating issues of societal concern.

The model of CATALISI is built upon 2 blocks:

- * **4 facilitators** (APRE, EY, ENOLL, F6S) - who will accelerate and facilitate the transformational pathways of HEIs through the acceleration services, the knowledge transfer, and the implementation of activities co-designed.
- * **7 implementers** (UCC, KTU, UJI, LUISS, UG, AUTH, VUMC) - the Higher Education Institutions that will implement new reforms in their structures intervening on specific domains and intervention areas.

Domains of Institutional transformation

Three main domains composed by different **intervention areas** indicate the content of specific institutional transformations.

DOMAIN 1

Research Careers and Talent Support

Recognition of qualifications & research careers

Reform of research assessment

Digitalization of higher education sector

Supporting talent circulation & mobility

Strengthening of human capital and addressing lifelong learning

Gender equality & inclusiveness

DOMAIN 2

Research modus operandi

Mainstreaming of open science and digitization of research

Enhanced public engagement and Outreach to society to solve social challenges

Sharing of research infrastructures and capacities

Reinforcing the role of universities in local innovation ecosystems

DOMAIN 3

Sustainable research and education

Sustainability in education (funding opportunities)

Sustainability in research

Sustainability in campus operations

CATALISI | Catalysation of institutional transformations of Higher Education Institutions through the adoption of acceleration services. Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement n. 101024272. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Acceleration services for Institutional transformation

Institutional transformations will be reached through the adoption of seven specific acceleration services, which are designed to facilitate and catalyze the process of institutional transformation of Higher Education Institutions, and are characterized by an innovative feature that crosses the domains.

Stakeholders are individuals or organizations that are involved, and/or interested in CATALISI activities, strategy and acceleration services. They are affected by CATALISI activities in some way or may have a direct impact on the Institutional transformation of HEIs.

Stakeholders represent all Quadruple Helix groups: government & public sector, industry & business, academia & universities, and civil society. Citizens and users are at the heart of the innovation ecosystem and are actors of the innovation process.

Identified stakeholders will contribute to the co-development of other acceleration services for the institutional transformation of higher education institutes.

ANNEX 4 – KTU ACTION PLAN

Intervention Area: Supporting talent circulation mobility GOAL: Foster first-time international mobility of staff

Activity: Conducting a survey of staff at pilot Faculty on obstacles and motivation for international mobility	
Leader	Aistė Balžekienė
Contributors	International coordinator of Faculty of Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities, KTU
Start date	April 2024
End date	November 2024
Milestones	Designing questionnaire, program online survey, dissemination of questionnaire, data analysis
Resources	Human resources (survey coordinator; data analyst; contacting person); technological resources (survey software; data analysis software)
Obstacles	(a) Low response rates of target group, (b) technical issues.
Mitigation measures	a) repeating invitations to participate, approaching individually target group; (b) using licensed survey software.
KPIs	Survey report
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Preparing the strategy on fostering first-time international mobility at KTU	
Leader	Aistė Balžekienė
Contributors	Academic Mobility office of KTU, International coordinator of Faculty of Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities, KTU; Study programme committees of FSSAH
Start date	September 2024
End date	December 2025
Milestone	Analysing the processes of international mobility, identifying the obstacles for first-time participation, preparing recommendations for institutional actions
Resource	Human resources (expert work), technical resources (editing, layout)
Obstacles	(a) time availability of contributors, (b) the upscaling of results from pilot faculty to KTU
Mitigation measures	(a - b) obtain the support from the university administration for the importance of this strategy
KPIs	Strategy document
Baseline value	0
Target value	1

Intervention area: Accurately addressing lifelong learning
GOAL: Develop a non-formal education strategy for KTU alumni

Activity: Establishing an institutional working group	
Leader	Audrone Telesiene
Contributors	Kaunas University of Technology Alumni Association; Kaunas University of Technology Rectors Office
Start date	March 2024
End date	September 2024
Milestone	Identifying purpose and objectives; stakeholder identification; membership recruitment; regular meetings
Resource	Human resources (expertise and members); time and commitment (time availability of the members); technological resources (collaboration tools); physical space (meeting rooms); support from leadership (endorsement)
Obstacles	(a) lack of leadership support; (b) conflicting priorities; (c) lack of time commitment
Mitigation measures	(a) obtain clear endorsement from top-level university leaders; (b) communicate the importance of the goal; (c) schedule meetings in advance
KPIs	Established working groups
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Survey of KTU alumni on the needs and suggestions for the lifelong learning with KTU	
Leader	Audrone Telesiene
Contributors	Kaunas University of Technology Alumni Association
Start date	April 2024
End date	December 2024
Milestone	Define the audience; design the questionnaire; activate an online survey collector
Resource	Human resources (survey coordinator; data analyst; contacting person); technological resources (survey software; data analysis software)
Obstacles	(a) Low response rates; (b) non-representative sample; (c) limited access to alumni contact information; (d) technical issues
Mitigation measures	(a) use trusted communication channels and repeat invitations several times; (b) promoting the survey widely and asking accurate conclusions; (c) collaborate with alumni association; (d) using a trusted survey platform.

KPIs	Alumni survey conducted
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Survey of bachelor's and master's students in their final year at KTU	
Leader	Audrone Telesiene
Contributors	Kaunas University of Technology education department
Start date	January 2025
End date	August 2025
Milestone	Define the audience; design the questionnaire; activate an online survey collector
Resource	Human resources (survey coordinator; data analyst; contacting person); technological resources (survey software; data analysis software)
Obstacles	(a) Low response rates; (b) non-representative sample; (c) limited access to students' contact information; (d) technical issues
Mitigation measures	(a) use trusted communication channels and repeat invitations several times; (b) promoting the survey widely and making accurate conclusions; (c) collaborate with education department at the KTU central administration office; (d) using a trusted survey platform.
KPIs	Student survey conducted
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Activity brief (including results of alumni survey and students's survey)	
Leader	Audrone Telesiene
Contributors	CATALISI KTU team memebtrs
Start date	September 2025
End date	December 2025
Milestone	Draft the Activity brief; edit the document
Resource	Templates and guidelines; human resources (for writing, editing and reviewing); time commitment.
Obstacles	(a) poor quality of writing; (b) poor quality of data visualization.
Mitigation measures	(a) conduct the internal review; (b) benefit from the advice of the KTU team and the wider CATALISI team of researchers.
KPIs	Activity brief
Baseline value	0
Target value	1

Intervention Area: Strengthening human capital
GOAL: Increase awareness of the academic staff about public engagement in research

Activity: Survey of Writing Clinic potential users	
Leader	Audrone Telesiene
Contributors	Doctoral school at the central administration of KTU; KTU Doctoral Students Association
Start date	March 2024
End date	December 2024
Milestone	Define the audience; design the questionnaire; activate an online survey collector
Resource	Human resources (survey coordinator; data analyst; contacting person); technological resources (survey software; data analysis software)
Obstacles	(a) Low response rates; (b) limited access to users' contact information; (c) technical issues
Mitigation measures	(a) use trusted communication channels and repeat invitations several times; (b) collaborate with Writing Clinic coordinators and KTU Doctoral school; (c) using trusted survey platform.
KPIs	Survey of doctoral students
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Interviews with Writing Clinic users	
Leader	Audrone Telesiene
Contributors	Writing Clinic coordinators at the Center of Foreign Languages, Kaunas University of Technology, Faculty of Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities
Start date	September 2024
End date	March 2025
Milestone	Recruit participants; schedule interviews
Resource	Human resources (interviewer); informed consent (consent form); interview protocol; technological tools for online meetings
Obstacles	(a) privacy concerns; (b) interviewer bias; (c) technical issues.
Mitigation measures	(a) obtain informed consent; (b) interviewer should have expertise in qualitative methods of social research; (c) use trusted meeting platforms.

KPIs	Writing Clinic user interviews
Baseline value	0
Target value	3
Activity: Announcing success stories or user testimonials in internal communication channels	
Leader	Audrone Telesiene
Contributors	Communication coordinators at the faculty; Writing Clinic coordinators at the Center of Foreign Languages, Kaunas University of Technology, Faculty of Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities
Start date	March 2025
End date	December 2025
Milestone	Identify success stories; craft messages; schedule launch of the messages
Resource	Human resources (content creator); access to internal communication channels (webpage, newsletter or similar)
Obstacles	(a) overemphasis on individual achievement; (b) privacy concerns; (c) inconsistent messaging.
Mitigation measures	(a) highlight collaboration and service provision; (b) obtain explicit consent; (c) ensure involvement of the communication specialists within the university.
KPIs	Messages published on internal communication channels
Baseline value	0
Target value	3
Activity: Action Plan (for strengthening of university based services for academic writing)	
Leader	Audrone Telesiene
Contributors	Writing Clinic coordinators at the Center of Foreign Languages, Kaunas University of Technology, Faculty of Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities
Start date	May 2025
End date	December 2025
Milestone	Articulate the objectives of the Action Plan; draft the Action Plan document
Resource	Human resources (expertise and writing); time and commitment (time availability); support from leadership (endorsement)
Obstacles	(a) lack of leadership support; (b) unclear timeline for possible actions; (c) resistance to change.
Mitigation measures	(a) obtain clear endorsement from top-level leaders; (b) involve the coordinators of the Writing Clinic; (c) communicate the importance of the goal
KPIs	Writing Clinic Service Enhancement Action Plan

Baseline value	0
Target value	1

Intervention Area: Public engagement with and outreach to society to solve social challenges

GOAL: Increase the competencies of academic staff to publish in highly-rated journals and books

Activity: Organize trainings for KTU researchers and public to increase awareness about citizen science	
Leader	Eglė Butkevičienė
Contributors	Research and Innovation Projects Centre, Department of Research Affairs of KTU, KTU Library, Citizen Science Hub, Faculty of Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities
Start date	September 2024
End date	May 2025
Milestone	Identification of potential audience; developing a content of the trainings, communicating information about trainings
Resource	Human resources (lecturers), time and commitment (time availability of the lecturer); technological resources (online tools, Moodle);
Obstacles	(a) lack of motivation of participants; (b) time constraints for researchers to participate in the event
Mitigation measures	(a) prepare and implement effective communication campaign; (b) prepare trainings in a way that they might be taken on self-study basis
KPIs	4 trainings for KTU researchers and public
Baseline value	0
Target value	4
Activity: To develop a strategy for effectively engaging public in research	
Leader	Eglė Butkevičienė
Contributors	Research and Innovation Projects Centre, Department of Research Affairs of KTU, KTU Library, Citizen science hub, Faculty of Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities
Start date	October 2024
End date	November 2025
Milestone	Collecting feedback from researchers about their needs, co-creating strategy, communicating strategy
Resource	Human resources (expert, researchers engaged in co-creation), technical resources (proofreading)
Obstacles	(a) skepticism about and lack of interest in the strategy from researchers, (b) low support from the highest levels of university management

Mitigation measures	(a) prepare and implement effective communication campaign; (b) communicate an added value of this perspective
KPIs	1 strategy
Baseline value	0
Target value	1

Intervention Area: Sustainability in research
GOAL: Strengthen interdisciplinary cooperation among KTU researchers

Activity : Organize B2B event for KTU researchers to strengthen interdisciplinary cooperation	
Leader	Aistė Balžekienė
Contributors	"Research and Innovation Projects Centre, Department of Research Affairs of KTU"
Start date	September 2024
End date	February 2025
Milestone	Identification of potential participants; deciding on the format and the content of the event, B2B event, post-event communication
Resource	Human resources (organization, contacting, moderating), financial resources (coffee breaks, printed materials), infrastructure (meeting place)
Obstacles	(a) time constraints for researchers to participate in the event (b) lack of motivation of participants
Mitigation measures	(a) obtain the support from the university research managers; (b) communicate the added values to the participants
KPIs	Event for KTU researchers
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Organize knowledge exchange event for PhD students to strengthen their interdisciplinary competencies	
Leader	Aistė Balžekienė
Contributors	"Doctoral School of KTU, Research and Innovation Projects Centre, KTU"
Start date	September 2024
End date	May 2025
Milestone	Identification of potential participants; deciding on the format and the content of the event, event for Phd students, post-event communication

Resource	Human resources (organization, contacting, moderating), financial resources (coffee breaks, printed materials), infrastructure (meeting place)
Obstacles	(a) time constraints for for top level researchers to participate in the knowledge exchange and support event, (b) lack of motivation of participants
Mitigation measures	(a) obtain the support from the university research managers; (b) communicate the added values to the participants
KPIs	Event for KTU PhD students
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Preparing recommendations for KTU on strengthening interdisciplinary cooperation	
Leader	Aistė Balžekienė
Contributors	"Research and Innovation Projects Centre, Department of Research Affairs of KTU, Doctoral School of KTU"
Start date	May 2024
End date	December 2025
Milestone	Analysing interdisciplinary cooperation processes, consultations with the contributors, preparation of recommendations, communication of the recommendations to the reserach community of KTU
Resource	Human resources (expert work, communication with contributors, analysis), technical resources (layout, proofreading)
Obstacles	(a) lack of leadership support; (b) unclear target groups for the recommendations
Mitigation measures	(a) obtain the support from the university administration for the importance of this activity; (b) clear definition of target groups for the recommendations
KPIs	Recommendations document
Baseline value	0
Target value	1

ANNEX 5 – UJI ACTION PLAN

Intervention Area: Research assessment and recognition of qualifications

GOAL: Review of UJI's evaluation policies

Activity: Reviewing UJI's current calls for proposals. In particular, UJI evaluation scale	
Leader	UJI
Contributors	CATALISI members, Vice-rectorate of research
Start date	Academic Year 2023/2024
End date	December 2025
Milestones	Academic year 2024/2025: Reviewing the Universitat Jaume I calls for applications (especially the "scale" and promotion plan); Reviewing national public calls for applications (especially the sexenios call for applications and new accreditation assessment systems. ANECA).
Resources	Human resources: CATALISI members, Vice-rectorate of research
Obstacles	No risks were identified
Mitigation measures	No mitigation measures needed
KPIs	Implementation of new standards for research assessment at UJI (following the UJI's adhesion to COARA). End of the project;
Baseline value	Changes in research assessment criteria at the national level
Target value	Adapting UJI's evaluation criteria to the new national guidelines
Leader	UJI
Contributors	CATALISI members, Vice-rectorate of research
Start date	Academic Year 2023/2024
End date	December 2025
Milestones	Academic year 2024/2025: Reviewing the Universitat Jaume I calls for applications (especially the "scale" and promotion plan); Reviewing national public calls for applications (especially the sexenios call for applications and new accreditation assessment systems. ANECA).
Resources	Human resources: CATALISI members, Vice-rectorate of research
Obstacles	No risks were identified
Mitigation measures	No mitigation measures needed

KPIs	Redefinition of UJI's evaluation scale for research outcomes. End of academic year 2023/2024.
Baseline value	Changes in research assessment criteria at the national level
Target value	Adapting UJI's evaluation criteria to the new national guidelines
Leader	UJI
Contributors	CATALISI members, Vice-rectorate of research
Start date	Academic Year 2023/2024
End date	December 2025
Milestones	Academic year 2024/2025: Reviewing the Universitat Jaume I calls for applications (especially the "scale" and promotion plan); Reviewing national public calls for applications (especially the sexenios call for applications and new accreditation assessment systems. ANECA).
Resources	Human resources: CATALISI members, Vice-rectorate of research
Obstacles	No risks were identified
Mitigation measures	No mitigation measures needed
KPIs	Implementation of new standards for research assessment at UJI (following the UJI's adhesion to COARA). Creation of a Chatbot for requesting reports on ethical evaluation. End of the project; Adaptation of specific points (on OA and/or integrity) in the ethical evaluation reports. End of the project
Baseline value	Changes in research assessment criteria at the national level
Target value	Adapting UJI's evaluation criteria to the new national guidelines

Intervention Area: Open Access

GOAL: Measure researchers' compliance with Open Access Policies

Activity: Creation of a small working group dedicated to the definition of indicators for the measurement of researchers' compliance with OA policies.	
Leader	UJI
Contributors	CATALISI members, UJI technical staff, top management and researchers
Start date	Academic Year 2023/2024
End date	December 2024
Milestones	Year 2023/2024: Defining a strategy to measure the research community's compliance with open access policies; year 2024/25: pilot development; September-December 2025: first tests on OA and collection of results.
Resources	Human resources: CATALISI members, UJI library, OCIT, Vice-rector of Research
Obstacles	Difficulty in the definition of the indicators. Also, difficulty creating awareness among researchers
Mitigation measures	Contacting experts and creating training materials for researchers
KPIs	initiate a collaborative process to define the main actions to be taken in terms of OA at the university (and define the indicators of measurement)
Baseline value	UJI's library already has some data on researchers' publications in OA journals
Target value	Indicators of measurement of OA fulfilment
Activity: Studying similar experiences (OA thermometer) implemented by other institutions	
Leader	UJI
Contributors	CATALISI members
Start date	Academic Year 2023/2024
End date	December 2024
Milestones	Same as the above
Resources	Human resources: CATALISI members

Obstacles	Difficulty accessing data
Mitigation measures	Contacting researchers involved in the initiative
KPIs	to learn about similar experiences in other institutions (including from other CATALISI members) to learn about similar experiences in other institutions (including from other CATALISI members)
Baseline value	There is a similar initiative at UAB
Target value	Exchanging knowledge with UAB and other institutions
Activity: Checking UJI's publication performance through UJI's database.	
Leader	UJI
Contributors	This will be carried out in collaboration with library services and OCIT.
Start date	Academic Year 2023/2024
End date	December 2025
Milestones	Year 2024/2025: Defining a new strategy to improve the position of UJI's open access journals or/and repositories
Resources	Human resources: CATALISI members, UJI library, OCIT
Obstacles	No risks were identified
Mitigation measures	No mitigation measures needed
KPIs	Being able to monitor the percentage of open access research carried out at UJI (UJI OA thermometer). End of the project
Baseline value	UJI's library already has some data on researchers' publications in OA journals
Target value	Complementing the already existing data with potentially a self-declaratory questionnaire for researchers about OA
Activity: Defining a new structure to strengthen the position of UJI's open access journals	
Leader	UJI
Contributors	This will be carried out in collaboration with library services, publications services and journal editors
Start date	Academic Year 2023/2024
End date	December 2024

Milestones	Year 2023/2024: Defining a new strategy to improve the position of UJI's open access journals or/and repositories
Resources	Human resources: CATALISI members, UJI library, OCIT
Obstacles	No risks were identified
Mitigation measures	No mitigation measures needed
KPIs	Strengthening the structure of UJI's Open Access journals. End of the project
Baseline value	UJI's set of Open Access journals
Target value	Improve UJI's journal performance

Intervention Area: Open Access, Research Assessment, Citizen Science, Gender Equality

GOAL: Creation of training materials

Activity: creation of short videos with concept definitions	
Leader	UJI
Contributors	CATALISI members, library, OCIT
Start date	Academic Year 2023/2024
End date	December 2025
Milestones	The academic year 2023/2024: definition of the areas of intervention that most urgently require training materials; definition of a communication and dissemination plan; Academic Year 2024/2025: drafts of the materials for the intervention areas that need to be targeted most urgently
Resources	Human resources: CATALISI members, library, OCIT
Obstacles	Difficulty defining concepts in a way that is rigorous but also accessible; creating engaging materials; spreading the materials among researchers
Mitigation measures	Collaborating with experts on the intervention areas but also experts on communication (at UJI)
KPIs	Creation of training materials. End of the project; Improving the performance of research ethics committees and their communication strategies addressing researchers
Baseline value	There are no short videos explaining basic concepts on citizen science, gender equality in research, research assessment and OA at UJI
Target value	Creating drafts for the videos

ANNEX 6 – AUTH ACTION PLAN

Intervention Area: Research Assessment - Recognition of qualifications

GOAL: Providing certifications and accreditation to LL and Citizen Science Participants

Activity: Review the existing policies and procedures related to qualification acknowledgment and professional advancement	
Leader	Evdokimos Konstantinidis
Contributors	Konstantina Tsimpita, Despoina Petsani, Pavlina Lazaridou
Start date	1-June
End date	Dec-24
Milestones	Identify any legal gaps or inconsistencies in the policies that need to be addressed. Providing guidance on best practices for drafting and implementing new policies that align with legal requirements.
Resources	Human resources (expertise and members from the Law Department); time and commitment (time availability of the members); technological resources (collaboration tools); physical space (meeting rooms); support from leadership (endorsement)
Obstacles	Organizational culture might affect how willing stakeholders are to participate in identifying areas for improvement. Cultural factors like hierarchy, communication norms, and attitudes toward change can influence how open people are to giving feedback and working together.
Mitigation measures	(a) Encourage collaboration among teams from diverse backgrounds to provide a range of perspectives during the policy review process. (b) clearly communicate the importance of the goal;
KPIs	How many individual policies or processes have been identified as candidates for revision or improvement. Target: Identify at least 10 specific policy elements or processes for revision.
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Map out the comprehensive processes involved in qualification recognition, career progression, and associated administrative procedures.	
Leader	Evdokimos Konstantinidis
Contributors	Konstantina Tsimpita, Despoina Petsani, Pavlina Lazaridou
Start date	1-June
End date	Dec-24

Milestones	Map out the comprehensive processes involved in qualification recognition, career progression, and associated administrative procedures. This includes integrating the knowledge and research work conducted within Living Labs (LL) into the university's structure.
Resources	Human resources (expertise and members from the Law Department); time and commitment (time availability of the members); technological resources (collaboration tools); physical space (meeting rooms); support from leadership (endorsement)
Obstacles	the absence of standardized criteria may lead to subjective interpretations and inconsistent evaluations across various processes, resulting in inaccuracies and differences in identifying areas for improvement.
Mitigation measures	
KPIs	Number of areas for improvement identified and prioritized. Target: Identify and prioritize at least 5 areas for improvement.
Baseline value	0
Target value	1

Intervention Area: Digitisation of Research
GOAL: Integrating MOOCs usage in the Medical Department

Activity: Integration of at least 3 Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) into the Medical Curriculum.

Leader	Vasiliki Kalfa
Contributors	Savvas Anastasiadis
Start date	1-Sep
End date	Dec-25
Milestones	Enrich the learning experience for students by providing access to high-quality educational resources beyond traditional classroom settings. Benefiting lifelong learners who are interested in advancing their knowledge and skills in the medical field.
Resources	Human resources (expertise and members from the Medical & IT Department); time and commitment (time availability of the members); technological resources (collaboration tools); physical space (meeting rooms); support from leadership (endorsement)
Obstacles	Intellectual property (IP) issues, as concerns may arise regarding the ownership and licensing agreements related to course content dissemination on MOOC platforms. Additionally, technical challenges may occur, including platform compatibility issues, infrastructure limitations, and connectivity problems.
Mitigation measures	(a) Encourage collaboration among teams from diverse backgrounds to provide a range of perspectives during the policy review process. (b) clearly communicate the importance of the goal;
KPIs	Number of people who are enrolled in at least one Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) offered by the Medical Department of Aristotle University Target: Achieve an enrolment of 100+ people, both medical students and externals
Baseline value	0
Target value	1

Activity: Engaging professors through seminars or “Train the Trainer” schemes.

Leader	Vasiliki Kalfa
Contributors	Savvas Anastasiadis
Start date	1-Sep
End date	Jun-25
Milestones	Empower educators with the knowledge and skills to effectively utilize MOOCs in their teaching practices, by providing guidance on how to engage relevant target groups, such as college students and learners outside of the university.
Resources	Human resources (expertise and members from the Medical & IT Department); time and commitment (time availability of the members); technological resources (collaboration tools); physical space (meeting rooms); support from leadership (endorsement)

Obstacles	Resistance to change from some professors or educators accustomed to traditional teaching methods may hinder the adoption of MOOCs
Mitigation measures	Overcoming this resistance requires effective communication, training, and support mechanisms
KPIs	Conduct specialized webinars aimed at empowering educators to effectively utilize MOOCs in teaching practices. Host at least 2 seminars within 2024, each with a minimum duration of 2 hours, ensuring active participation from a minimum of 20 professors or educators per seminar
Baseline value	0
Target value	1

Intervention Area: Mainstreaming of Open Science & Sustainability in Research

GOAL: Facilitating Fair Data & IP Sharing

Activity: Create a dedicated lecture in the Medical Department's Innovation Course (Selected course for the 1st Year Medical Students), focusing on the practice of sharing data during academic education.	
Leader	Panagiotis Bamidis
Contributors	Evdokimos Konstantinidis, Despoina Petsani
Start date	1-Sep
End date	Jan-25
Milestones	The main goal is to enhance awareness among students and future researchers about the importance of open data sharing in the medical field.
Resources	Human resources (expertise and members from the Medical & IT Department); time and commitment (time availability of the members); technological resources (collaboration tools); physical space (lecture rooms); support from leadership (endorsement)
Obstacles	1) challenges due to limited prior exposure to concepts of open data sharing. 2) Standardization of the lecture's teaching in the upcoming years. 3) understanding the technical aspects of data sharing platforms, protocols, and tools may pose difficulties.
Mitigation measures	1) Preparation of lecture materials, case studies, and practical exercises that can be easily integrated into the course syllabus each year, facilitating continuity and depth of learning. 2) Hands-on Training Sessions: Organize hands-on training sessions or tutorials focused on the technical aspects of data sharing platforms, protocols, and tools.
KPIs	Measure the percentage of students who select the course and conducting their final presentation on this topic. Target: At least 20 registered students
Baseline value	0
Target value	1

Activity: Providing training sessions for users, particularly researchers, on the principles and practices of data sharing

Leader	Evdokimos Konstantinidis
Contributors	Savvas Anastasiadis
Start date	1-Mar
End date	Jun-25
Milestones	This collaboration with the Technology Transfer Office aims to educate attendees on the types of data that can be shared, best practices for data sharing, and the potential benefits of open data sharing in research..
Resources	Human resources (expertise and members from IT Department and Technology Transfer Office); time and commitment (time availability of the members); technological resources (collaboration tools); physical space (meeting rooms); support from leadership (endorsement)
Obstacles	A challenge for researchers is the fear of data misuse or legal consequences, as well as time constraints, which may isolate them from actively engaging in data sharing practices.
Mitigation measures	1) Collaborative partnerships with other departments, student organizations, or external stakeholders who share an interest in the topics covered in the training sessions. 2) Launch a targeted promotional campaign to increase awareness and generate interest in the training sessions
KPIs	i) Topics to be covered: data management, data sharing platforms and tools, data privacy and security, and legal and ethical considerations. ii) Number of attendees at each training session. Target: Achieve a minimum attendance of 25 attendees per training session.
Baseline value	0
Target value	1

ANNEX 7 – LUISS ACTION PLAN

Intervention Area: Supporting talent circulation/mobility
GOAL: Short-Term: MSCA and ERC applications

Activity: Communication of funding opportunities through monthly communications	
Leader	Research & Third Mission Office
Contributors	Subcontractors
Start date	1/1/2023
End date	31/12/2024
Milestones	Scouting of opportunities; drafting of communication; sending of communication to target audience
Resources	Human resources; technological resources
Obstacles	None
Mitigation measures	N/A
KPIs	Number of communications (funding opportunities) shared
Baseline value	0
Target value	20
Activity: Organisations of seminars with a focus on MSCA and ERC opportunities	
Leader	Research & Third Mission Office
Contributors	Events Office
Start date	1/1/2023
End date	31/12/2024
Milestones	Identification of potential audience and speakers; development of content for the seminars; logistical organisation; communication of information about seminars
Resources	Human resources; technological resources; financial resources
Obstacles	Lack of participation
Mitigation measures	Engaging communication
KPIs	Number of seminars organised
Baseline value	0
Target value	2
Activity: Sponsorisation of external seminars (training opportunities) through communications	

Leader	Research & Third Mission Office
Contributors	N/A
Start date	1/1/2023
End date	31/12/2024
Milestones	Scouting of opportunities; drafting of communication; sending of communication to target audience
Resources	Human resources; technological resources
Obstacles	None
Mitigation measures	N/A
KPIs	Number of communications (training opportunities) shared
Baseline value	0
Target value	10
Activity: Support to faculty for ERC and MSCA applications	
Leader	Research & Third Mission Office
Contributors	Subcontractors
Start date	1/1/2023
End date	31/12/2024
Milestones	N/A
Resources	Human resources
Obstacles	Late request by the faculty
Mitigation measures	Standardised process
KPIs	Number of applications submitted
Baseline value	0
Target value	10

Intervention Area: Supporting talent circulation/mobility
GOAL: Medium-Term: Improved LUISS' policies to attract ERC and MSCA talents

Activity: Update/addition of incentives to LUISS policies for talent attraction	
Leader	Vice-rector for Research
Contributors	Research & Third Mission Office
Start date	1/1/2025
End date	31/12/2025
Milestones	Review of current policies; assessment of needs; assessment of administrative and financial constraints; drafting of updated policy; approval of the policy
Resources	Human resources; financial resources
Obstacles	- Lack of internal support - Lack of funding available
Mitigation measures	Internal advocacy
KPIs	Number of incentives updated/added
Baseline value	0
Target value	2

Intervention Area: Supporting talent circulation/mobility

GOAL: Long-Term: Increased funds for research excellence projects

Activity: Continue short and medium term actions	
Leader	Research & Third Mission Office
Contributors	TBC
Start date	1/1/2026
End date	31/12/2028
Milestones	N/A
Resources	Human resources; technological resources; financial resources
Obstacles	TBC
Mitigation measures	TBC
KPIs	- Volume of funding (in Euro) for the year - Number of funded projects
Baseline value	TBC
Target value	TBC

Intervention Area: Mainstreaming of open science and digitalisation of research

GOAL: Short-Term goal: Awareness about Open Science

Activity: Desk research of EU guidelines on OS	
Leader	Research & Third Mission Office
Contributors	N/A
Start date	1/1/2023
End date	31/12/2024
Milestones	Desk research; drafting of written documentation
Resources	Human resources
Obstacles	None
Mitigation measures	N/A
KPIs	Written documentation produced
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Update of Luiss webpage with resources for OA and OS	
Leader	Research & Third Mission Office
Contributors	N/A
Start date	1/1/2023
End date	31/12/2024
Milestones	N/A
Resources	Human resources
Obstacles	None
Mitigation measures	N/A
KPIs	Update completed
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Assessment of the state of the art on the topic among LUISS faculty	
Leader	Research & Third Mission Office

Contributors	Studies & Evaluation Office
Start date	1/1/2023
End date	31/12/2024
Milestones	Identification of the audience; design of the questionnaire; set up of the online survey; analysis of data
Resources	Human resources; technological resources
Obstacles	Lack of participation
Mitigation measures	Engaging communication
KPIs	Written output produced
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Hold trainings on tools to publish in Open Science for European projects (Horizon Europe requirements: what can be considered Open Science and which are the different types of editors," pure" open access or hybrid)	
Leader	Research & Third Mission Office
Contributors	Events Office
Start date	1/1/2023
End date	31/12/2024
Milestones	Identification of potential audience and speakers; development of content for the trainings; logistical organisation; communication of information about trainings
Resources	Human resources; technological resources; financial resources
Obstacles	Lack of participation
Mitigation measures	Engaging communication
KPIs	Training completed
Baseline value	0
Target value	1

Intervention Area: Mainstreaming of open science and digitalisation of research

GOAL: Medium-Term: Quality publications in Open Access

Activity: Update of the 2016 OA Policy and drafting of OS Policy (single document)	
Leader	Research & Third Mission Office
Contributors	- Library - Vice-rector for Research - Heads of Departments
Start date	1/1/2025
End date	31/12/2025
Milestones	Review of current policies; assessment of needs; assessment of administrative and financial constraints; drafting of updated policy; approval of the policy
Resources	Human resources; financial resources
Obstacles	Lack of internal support
Mitigation measures	Internal advocacy
KPIs	Approved policy including updated OA rules and new OS rules
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Provision of incentives to publish in Open Access, connected to internal research evaluation criteria	
Leader	Vice-rector for Research
Contributors	- Library - Research & Third Mission Office - Heads of Departments
Start date	1/1/2025
End date	31/12/2025
Milestones	Review of current criteria; assessment of needs; assessment of administrative and financial constraints; drafting of updated criteria; approval of the regulation
Resources	Human resources; financial resources

Obstacles	Lack of internal support
Mitigation measures	Internal advocacy
KPIs	Updated internal research evaluation criteria
Baseline value	0
Target value	1

Intervention Area: Mainstreaming of open science and digitalisation of research

GOAL: Long-Term: Adoption of Open Science practices

Activity: Development of innovative tools/instruments for OS	
Leader	Research & Third Mission Office
Contributors	-IT Department - Subcontractors
Start date	1/1/2026
End date	31/12/2028
Milestones	TBC
Resources	Human resources; technological resources; financial resources
Obstacles	- Lack of internal support - Lack of funding available
Mitigation measures	Internal advocacy
KPIs	Tools/instruments to support OS developed
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Review of internal regulations for research incentives connected to OS	
Leader	Vice-rector for Research
Contributors	Research & Third Mission Office
Start date	1/1/2026
End date	31/12/2028
Milestones	Review of current policies; assessment of needs; assessment of administrative and financial constraints; drafting of updated policy; approval of the policy
Resources	Human resources; financial resources
Obstacles	- Lack of internal support - Lack of funding available

Mitigation measures	Internal advocacy
KPIs	Number of incentives updated/added
Baseline value	0
Target value	2

Intervention Area: Public engagement with and outreach to society to solve social challenges

GOAL: Short-Term: Awareness towards Third Mission

Activity: Launch of questionnaires on the awareness on TM in general, and on what Luiss does in the field, with the goal of monitoring, starting from now, the awareness of the Faculty and the administrative staff

Leader	Research & Third Mission Office
Contributors	Studies & Evaluation Office
Start date	1/1/2023
End date	31/12/2024
Milestones	Identification of the audience; design of the questionnaire; set up of the online survey; analysis of data
Resources	Human resources; technological resources
Obstacles	Lack of participation
Mitigation measures	Engaging communication
KPIs	Questionnaires completed
Baseline value	0
Target value	1

Activity: Presentation of the Third Mission Office and its activities to LUISS faculty and other administrative offices

Leader	Research & Third Mission Office
Contributors	N/A
Start date	1/1/2023
End date	31/12/2024
Milestones	N/A
Resources	Human resources
Obstacles	None
Mitigation measures	N/A
KPIs	Presentation completed
Baseline value	0

Target value	1
Activity: Creation of multimedia contents to support the presentations, and to be included on the website	
Leader	Research & Third Mission Office
Contributors	- Subcontractors - Digital Transformation Office
Start date	1/1/2023
End date	31/12/2024
Milestones	N/A
Resources	Human resources; technological resources; financial resources
Obstacles	None
Mitigation measures	N/A
KPIs	Content created and published
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Restyling of the University website to enhance the TM and public engagement	
Leader	Research & Third Mission Office
Contributors	Digital Transformation Office
Start date	1/1/2023
End date	31/12/2024
Milestones	N/A
Resources	Human resources; technological resources
Obstacles	None
Mitigation measures	N/A
KPIs	Website updated
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Participation to multiple courses on Third Mission and to the activities of the networks and national consortia to be up-to-date (by CODAU, CRUI, etc.)	
Leader	Research & Third Mission Office
Contributors	N/A
Start date	1/1/2023

End date	31/12/2024
Milestones	N/A
Resources	Human resources; financial resources
Obstacles	None
Mitigation measures	N/A
KPIs	Number of courses/seminars attended
Baseline value	0
Target value	15
Activity: Update of the Research newsletter to include TM	
Leader	Research & Third Mission Office
Contributors	N/A
Start date	1/1/2023
End date	31/12/2024
Milestones	N/A
Resources	Human resources; technological resources
Obstacles	None
Mitigation measures	N/A
KPIs	Newsletter updated
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Organise an event to promote LUISS research to the wider public (LUISS Research Day)	
Leader	Vice-rector for Research
Contributors	- Departments Offices - Research & Third Mission Office - Events Office
Start date	1/1/2023
End date	31/12/2024
Milestones	Identification of potential audience and speakers; development of content for the event; logistical organisation; communication of information about the event
Resources	Human resources; technological resources; financial resources
Obstacles	Lack of participation
Mitigation measures	Engaging communication

KPIs	Event organised
Baseline value	0
Target value	1

Intervention Area: Public engagement with and outreach to society to solve social challenges
GOAL: Medium-Term: Quality of Third Mission activities and involvement of faculty

Activity: Identification of best practices of strategies for the improvement of monitoring activities and the strengthening of university results

Leader	Research & Third Mission Office
Contributors	- Studies & Evaluation Office - QA Office
Start date	1/1/2025
End date	31/12/2025
Milestones	Review of current policies; assessment of needs; drafting of updated guidelines
Resources	Human resources
Obstacles	None
Mitigation measures	N/A
KPIs	Written documentation
Baseline value	0
Target value	1

Activity: Training and updating activities for the faculty on the topics of communication of research and public engagement, also with the goal of participating to European funding activities (ex. MSCA and Citizens actions)

Leader	Research & Third Mission Office
Contributors	Events Office
Start date	1/1/2025
End date	31/12/2025
Milestones	Identification of potential audience and speakers; development of content for the trainings; logistical organisation; communication of information about trainings
Resources	Human resources; technological resources; financial resources
Obstacles	Lack of participation
Mitigation measures	Engaging communication
KPIs	Number of new trainings organised

Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Update of the LUISS strategic documents to include objectives with regards to TM	
Leader	University Board
Contributors	- Studies & Evaluation Office - Research & Third Mission Office
Start date	1/1/2025
End date	31/12/2025
Milestones	Review of current documents; identification of strategic goals; drafting of updated sections; approval of the documents
Resources	Human resources
Obstacles	None
Mitigation measures	N/A
KPIs	Inclusion of TM in LUISS strategic documents
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Restyling of the University website to enhance the TM and public engagement	
Leader	Research & Third Mission Office
Contributors	Digital Transformation Office
Start date	1/1/2025
End date	31/12/2025
Milestones	N/A
Resources	Human resources; technological resources
Obstacles	None
Mitigation measures	N/A
KPIs	Website updated
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Application to the MSCA and Citizens Actions Call	
Leader	Research & Third Mission Office
Contributors	- Faculty - Subcontractor

Start date	1/1/2025
End date	31/12/2025
Milestones	N/A
Resources	Human resources
Obstacles	Late request by the faculty
Mitigation measures	Standardised process
KPIs	Number of applications submitted
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Addition of incentives to LUISS policies to enhance faculty and administrative staff involvement in public engagement activities	
Leader	Director of Research and Governance
Contributors	- Research & Third Mission Office - Vice-rector for Research
Start date	1/1/2025
End date	31/12/2025
Milestones	Review of current criteria; assessment of needs; assessment of administrative and financial constraints; drafting of updated criteria; approval of the regulation
Resources	Human resources; financial resources
Obstacles	- Lack of internal support - Lack of funding available
Mitigation measures	Internal advocacy
KPIs	Number of incentives added
Baseline value	0
Target value	2

Intervention Area: Public engagement with and outreach to society to solve social challenges

GOAL: Long-term: Role in the national and international debate on Third Mission

Activity: Increase participation to national and international networks on the topic	
Leader	Research & Third Mission Management
Contributors	Research & Third Mission Office
Start date	1/1/2026
End date	31/12/2028
Milestones	N/A
Resources	Human resources; financial resources
Obstacles	TBC
Mitigation measures	TBC
KPIs	Number of networks LUISS is part of
Baseline value	TBC
Target value	TBC

ANNEX 8 – AUMC ACTION PLAN

Intervention Area: Reform of research assessment & recognition of qualifications and research career

GOAL: Embedding RI education sustainably to increase RCR and research culture

Activity: Structural revisions on RCR curricula	
Leader	
Contributors	RI Coordinators and academic staff involved in RCR training
Start date	Feb-24
End date	spring 2025
Milestones	Re-design RCR curricula
Resources	
Obstacles	Lack of reach Lack of time and commitment Fear of losing ownership of own training
Mitigation measures	Focus-group/co-creation sessions
KPIs	Establish a network of trainers in RCR within RIOS
Baseline value	
Target value	
Activity: Discipline specific training in RCR	
Leader	
Contributors	RI Coordinators and academic staff involved in RCR training
Start date	end 24
End date	Dec-25
Milestones	RCR courses in all Faculties
Resources	
Obstacles	Lack of time and commitment Skepticism (RI seen as irrelevant)
Mitigation measures	Co-creation sessions and active engagement

KPIs	RCR courses in all 10 Faculties
Baseline value	
Target value	
Activity: Implementation of the re-designed RCR PhD courses in each Faculty	
Leader	
Contributors	RI Coordinators and academic staff involved in RCR training
Start date	spring 24
End date	Dec-25
Milestones	Sustainable embedding of RCR training
Resources	
Obstacles	Lack of time and commitment
Mitigation measures	Co-creation sessions and active engagement
KPIs	minimum of 50 PhD students trained
Baseline value	
Target value	

Activity: Help develop trainings for supervisors: set a default, help with the development of a toolbox and training framework

Leader	
Contributors	CATALISI, trainers, RIOS
Start date	Feb-24
End date	Feb-25
Milestones	Re-design RCR curricula
Resources	
Obstacles	
Mitigation measures	
KPIs	Supervisor training toolbox and framework
Baseline value	
Target value	

Activity: Introduce peer coach system

Leader	
Contributors	HR, CTL, RIOS
Start date	Fall 24
End date	Dec-25
Milestones	Build networks
Resources	
Obstacles	Lack of time to participate, lack of awareness

Mitigation measures	Increase engagement, connect to policy
KPIs	Peer coach system
Baseline value	
Target value	
Activity: create network for trainers	
Leader	
Contributors	CTL
Start date	Fall 24
End date	Dec-25
Milestones	Build networks
Resources	
Obstacles	Lack of time for trainers
Mitigation measures	Adapt activities to trainer needs
KPIs	Network, meeting twice a year
Baseline value	
Target value	
Activity: implement pilot trainings and evaluate	
Leader	
Contributors	CATALISI, RIOS
Start date	Summer 24
End date	Summer 25
Milestones	Sustainable embedding of RCR training
Resources	
Obstacles	Lack of general overview trainings
Mitigation measures	Connect to relevant trainers and policymakers, jointly implement and evaluate trainings
KPIs	Paper on evaluation
Baseline value	
Target value	

Activity: Develop a RI toolbox for organizing RI activities such as workshops	
Leader	
Contributors	RI coordinators, RI policy people, RI ambassadors / RIOS
Start date	Sep-24
End date	Dec-25
Milestones	Sustainable embedding of RCR education
Resources	
Obstacles	Lack of time + resources relevant people need to be included
Mitigation measures	Engage, organize co-creation and awareness workshops
KPIs	Toolbox for organizing RI activities on the website
Baseline value	
Target value	
Activity: Develop an overview of all RI instruments available at VU and Amsterdam UMC	
Leader	
Contributors	RIOS (in the lead) Stephanie van de Sandt – infra-expert CATALISI
Start date	Apr-24
End date	Dec-25
Milestones	Sustainable embedding of RCR education
Resources	
Obstacles	Sustainability after RIOS

Mitigation measures	Connect to policy
KPIs	Provide overview RI instruments
Baseline value	
Target value	
Activity: Map the group non/academic staff / who are they and what are thier training needs	
Leader	
Contributors	CATALISI, the group self
Start date	Sep-24
End date	Sep-25
Milestones	
Resources	
Obstacles	Lack of overview, who to involve in mapping, how to categorize
Mitigation measures	Use snowball sampling through own network
KPIs	Present overview of non-academic staff
Baseline value	
Target value	
Activity: Map research support staff and training needs	
Leader	
Contributors	Center for teaching and learning, research support
Start date	Sep-24
End date	Sep-25
Milestones	
Resources	
Obstacles	Lack of overview, who to involve in mapping, how to categorize
Mitigation measures	Use snowball sampling through own network

KPIs	Present overview of research support staff
Baseline value	
Target value	

ANNEX 9 – UCC ACTION PLAN

Intervention Area: Sustainability of Research Finance

Goal: Explore, identify and articulate financing issues for sustainability in research

Activity: Establish an 'Action Plan' taskforce team as Steering Group for the Action Plan phases:	
Leader	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact
Contributors	Research Office; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Action Plan Taskforce
Start date	Mar-24
End date	Dec-24
Milestones	First taskforce meeting
Resources	Recrutiment following validation workshop
Obstacles	Securing commitment from key staff
Mitigation measures	Draft Action Plan Validation Workshop
KPIs	Taskforce TOR
Baseline value	0
Target value	1

Intervention Area: Sustainability of Research Finance

Goal: Co-Creation Framework and Acceleration Services

Activity: Devise Co-Creation Framework and Management - integrated approach to design, development, delivery of living-lab co-creation activities linked to GOALS	
Leader	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact
Contributors	Research Office; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Action Plan Taskforce
Start date	Mar-24
End date	Jun-24
Milestones	Draft in May to inform planning for data gathering + co-creation
Resources	Internal data gathering and compilation existing information; technical / financial knowledge
Obstacles	inherent tensions / diverse narratives and understandings of issues
Mitigation measures	identifying clear framework and narrative for activities that recognises inherent tensions and need to build understanding
KPIs	Framework and workplan for activities
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Research Culture: Acceleration services - Map acceleration services activities to the goals	
Leader	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact
Contributors	Research Office; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Action Plan Taskforce
Start date	Mar-24
End date	Sep-24
Milestones	Draft in May to inform Co-Creation Framework and Model
Resources	Meetings and desktop. Brokering, matchmaking and building connections for the best impact
Obstacles	Building buy-in with key stakeholders
Mitigation measures	Draft Action Plan Validation Workshop and subsequent one-to-one meetings
KPIs	Acceleration Services Map
Baseline value	0
Target value	1

Activity: Establish a Living Lab on financial sustainability in HEI research

Leader	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact
Contributors	Research Office; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Action Plan Taskforce
Start date	Dec-24
End date	Dec-25
Milestones	Co-creation activities from each of the goals
Resources	Ongoing work of AP Taskforce
Obstacles	Not achieving strategic alignment and impact
Mitigation measures	Recruitment of key influencers / decision makers to AP Taskforce. Mobilising comms/dissemination to ensure meaningful rollout of Action Plan
KPIs	Articulate issues and Living Lab in a position paper
Baseline value	0
Target value	1

Intervention Area: Sustainability of Research Finance

Goal: Co-Create Revised Overhead Model (Indirect Costs)

Activity: Current State - Desktop review and articulate detailed current state as a foundational tool for engagement and communications

Leader	Research Office
Contributors	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Action Plan Taskforce
Start date	Mar-24
End date	Jun-24
Milestones	Draft in May to inform planning for data gathering + co-creation
Resources	Internal data gathering and compilation existing information; technical / financial knowledge
Obstacles	inherent tensions / diverse narratives and understandings of issues
Mitigation measures	identifying clear framework and narrative for activities that recognises inherent tensions and need to build understanding
KPIs	Current State Overview Report
Baseline value	0
Target value	1

Activity: Research Costs Data and Insights - Survey to deepen understanding and insights of research needs and spend direct/indirect costs

Leader	Research Office
Contributors	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Action Plan Taskforce
Start date	Jun-24
End date	Dec-24
Milestones	Draft Report to inform communications
Resources	Data gathering and analysis
Obstacles	low response rates; diverse levels of capacity across the organisation
Mitigation measures	first co-creation event to mobilise and build a common understanding of Goal and activities
KPIs	Survey report
Baseline value	0

Target value	1
Activity: Identify best international practices in other jurisdictions and learn from CATALASI partners how other institutions handle overhead and income allocation.	
Leader	Strategic Planning and Institutional Research
Contributors	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact; Research Office; Action Plan Taskforce; CATALASI/Other Networks/Partners
Start date	Mar-24
End date	Dec-24
Milestones	June: identify key cases to explore
Resources	Desk research; acceleration services; meetings/exchanges
Obstacles	Identifying which models we can learn most from, have best applicability for UCC
Mitigation measures	First milestone to identify key cases will consider a 'long list' of options and devise rationale for selected cases
KPIs	Develop 3 x international case examples
Baseline value	0
Target value	3
Activity: Scope and Brief for co-design overhead model	
Leader	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact
Contributors	Research Office; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Action Plan Taskforce + Key Internal Stakeholders
Start date	Nov-24
End date	Mar-25
Milestones	Jan 25 gather inputs from contributors
Resources	Desktop, meetings and co-creation skills/interaction design expertise
Obstacles	Poorly devised scope and brief will reduce potential for co-designing a fit for purpose over-head model
Mitigation measures	Development work with AP Taskforce; interaction design expertise and Research Office to for a clear 'Co-Design' Brief and co-design process
KPIs	Co-Design Brief
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Co-design an ideal over-head model (indirect costs) - Deliver 3 x co-design workshops to engage internal stakeholders in the design and development of a new model	
Leader	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact

Contributors	Research Office; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Action Plan Taskforce + Living Lab stakeholders
Start date	Apr-25
End date	Sep-25
Milestones	Co-creation workshops - May 24; Feb 25; Sept 25
Resources	Desktop, meetings and co-creation skills/interaction design expertise
Obstacles	Not achieving strategic alignment and impact
Mitigation measures	Recruitment of key influencers / decision makers to AP Taskforce. Workshop attendees to extend to widen alignment and impact
KPIs	Co-design workshops on overhead model
Baseline value	0
Target value	3
Activity: Culture and Communications - Disseminate co-designed model	
Leader	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact
Contributors	Research Office; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Comms;
Start date	Dec-24
End date	Dec-25
Milestones	Final Workshop Sept 25
Resources	Content development; Workshop outputs; News item to promote the co-designed model
Obstacles	Lacking visibility / impact
Mitigation measures	Identify comms action to promote to national fora
KPIs	News item and co-design model as output for dissemination
Baseline value	0
Target value	2

Intervention Area: Sustainability in Research Finance

Goal: Co-Create Engaged Research funding model

Activity: Current State - Desktop review, policy and insitutional context as foundational tool building understanding of engaged research	
Leader	Research Office
Contributors	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Action Plan Taskforce
Start date	Mar-24
End date	Jun-24
Milestones	Draft in May to inform planning for data gathering + co-creation
Resources	Internal data gathering and compilation existing information; technical / financial knowledge
Obstacles	Complexity of topic, need to build capacity and awareness
Mitigation measures	Current state to 'keep it simple' to support foundational understanding for future actions
KPIs	Current State Overview Report
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Engaged Research Data and Insights - Engaged Research focus groups to deepen understanding and insights	
Leader	Research Office
Contributors	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Action Plan Taskforce
Start date	June-24
End date	Dec-24
Milestones	Draft Report to inform communications
Resources	Data gathering and analysis
Obstacles	Low response rates; diverse levels of capacity across org
Mitigation measures	Current state to 'keep it simple' to support foundational understanding for future actions
KPIs	Focus group report
Baseline value	0
Target value	1

Activity: Identify best international practice in other jurisdictions and learn from CATALASI partners	
Leader	Strategic Planning and Institutional Research
Contributors	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact; Research Office; Action Plan Taskforce; CATALSI/Other Networks/Partners
Start date	Mar-24
End date	Mar-25
Milestones	June: identify key cases to explore
Resources	Desk research; acceleration services; meetings/exchanges
Obstacles	Identifying which models we can learn most from, have best applicability for UCC
Mitigation measures	First milestone to identify key cases will consider a 'long list' of options and devise rationale for selected cases
KPIs	Develop 3 x international case examples
Baseline value	0
Target value	3
Activity: Scope and Brief for pilot UCC Engaged Research Funding Model - outline scope and brief for co-designing Engaged Research Model	
Leader	Research Culture, Engagement, and Impact
Contributors	Research Office; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Action Plan Taskforce + Key Internal Stakeholders
Start date	Nov-24
End date	Mar-25
Milestones	Jan 25: gather inputs from contributors
Resources	Desktop, meetings and co-creation skills/interaction design expertise
Obstacles	Poorly devised scope and brief will reduce potential for co-designing activities.
Mitigation measures	Development work with AP Taskforce; interaction design expertise and Research Office to for a clear 'Co-Design' Brief and co-design process
KPIs	Co-design scope and brief
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Co-design an ER model to pilot in UCC	
Leader	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact
Contributors	Research Office; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Action Plan Taskforce + Living Lab stakeholders
Start date	Apr-24
End date	Sep-25

Milestones	Mar 25: Co-creation workshop
Resources	Desktop, meetings and co-creation skills/interaction design expertise
Obstacles	Ensuring mechanisms in place for practical application/implementation of potential pilot
Mitigation measures	Preparatory work to secure support for practical implementation.
KPIs	ER Model Pilot Articulated
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Culture and Communications - Launch ER Model	
Leader	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact
Contributors	Research Office; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Comms;
Start date	Dec-24
End date	Dec-25
Milestones	Sep 25: Pilot launch
Resources	Communications oversight and coordination
Obstacles	Content and pilot development post co-design workshop
Mitigation measures	Identify comms action to build leadership awareness and commitment
KPIs	Launch of pilot Action to initiate ER Model - associated news/notice for dissemination (web + workvivo)
Baseline value	0
Target value	1

Intervention Area: Sustainability of Research Finance

Goal: Co-Create and Pilot New Income Models

Activity: Current State - Desktop review and articulate high level current state context on priority areas of focus for capacity building considering e.g. PhD Funding model, multi-inter-trans-disciplinary co-operation; talent; career progression and diversification of staff research, participation and performance	
Leader	Research Office
Contributors	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Action Plan Taskforce
Start date	Mar-24
End date	Jun-24
Milestones	Draft in May to inform planning for data gathering + co-creation
Resources	Internal data gathering and compilation existing information; technical / financial knowledge
Obstacles	Clarity of purpose and remit
Mitigation measures	Current state to establish clear expectations for engagement with stakeholders
KPIs	Current State Overview Report
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Strategic Research Fund Data and Insights - One to one meetings with senior leadership on aligning with institutional strategy implementation	
Leader	Research Office
Contributors	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Action Plan Taskforce
Start date	Jun-24
End date	Dec-24
Milestones	Draft Report to inform communications
Resources	Data gathering and analysis
Obstacles	low response rates; definition of 'capacity building'
Mitigation measures	Data and insights to allow for qualitative and quantitative
KPIs	Survey report

Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Identify best international practice in other jurisdictions and learn from CATALASI partner institutions structures and mechanisms to support financial investment in building capacity (talent and research support systems/infrastructure)	
Leader	Strategic Planning and Institutional Research
Contributors	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact; Research Office; Action Plan Taskforce; CATALSI/Other Networks/Partners
Start date	Mar-24
End date	Dec-24
Milestones	June identify key cases to explore
Resources	Desk research; acceleration services; meetings/exchanges
Obstacles	Identifying which models we can learn most from, have best applicability for UCC
Mitigation measures	First milestone to identify key cases will consider a 'long list' of options and devise rationale for selected cases
KPIs	Develop 3 x international case examples
Baseline value	0
Target value	3
Activity: Scope and Brief for a Strategic Research Fund - outline co-design scope and brief of a strategic research fund focussed on supporting e.g. talent, career progression and capacity building	
Leader	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact
Contributors	Research Office; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Action Plan Taskforce + Key Internal Stakeholders
Start date	Nov-24
End date	Mar-25
Milestones	Jan 25 gather inputs from contributors
Resources	Desktop, meetings and co-creation skills/interaction design expertise
Obstacles	Poorly devised scope and brief will reduce potential for co-designing activities.
Mitigation measures	Development work with AP Taskforce; integration design expertise and Research Office to for a clear 'Co-Design' Brief and co-design process. One to ones with additional key internal depts as required
KPIs	Co-design scope and brief
Baseline value	0

Target value	1
Activity: Co-design strategic research fund pilot actions	
Leader	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact
Contributors	Research Office; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Action Plan Taskforce + Living Lab stakeholders
Start date	Apr-25
End date	Sep-25
Milestones	Co-creation workshop - May 25
Resources	Desktop, meetings and co-creation skills/interaction design expertise
Obstacles	Ensuring mechanisms in place for practical application/implementation of potential pilot actions
Mitigation measures	Preparatory work to secure support for practical implementation.
KPIs	Co-creation event
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Culture and Communications - Launch strategic research fund pilot actions	
Leader	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact
Contributors	Research Office; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Comms;
Start date	Dec-24
End date	Dec-25
Milestones	Launch pilot Sept 25
Resources	Content and pilot development post co-design workshop
Obstacles	Not embedded in the wider strategic planning of the University
Mitigation measures	Identify comms action to build leadership awareness and commitment
KPIs	Launch of pilot action(s) - associated news/notice for dissemination
Baseline value	0
Target value	1

Intervention Area: Sustainability of Research Finance

Goal: Co-create and Pilot Strategic Research Fund

Activity: Current State - Desktop review and articulate detailed current state as foundational tool for engagement and communications	
Leader	Research Office
Contributors	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Action Plan Taskforce
Start date	Mar-24
End date	Jun-24
Milestones	Draft in May to inform planning for data gathering + co-creation
Resources	Internal data gathering and compilation existing information; technical / financial knowledge
Obstacles	Part of national funding/policy landscape
Mitigation measures	Current state to capture the external factors
KPIs	Current State Overview Report
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Income Models Data and Insights -	
Leader	Research Office
Contributors	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Action Plan Taskforce
Start date	Jun-24
End date	Dec-24
Milestones	Draft Report to inform communications
Resources	Data gathering and analysis
Obstacles	low response rates; Part of national funding/policy landscape
Mitigation measures	Data and insights to engage external
KPIs	Survey report
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Identify best international practice in other jurisdictions and learn from CATALASI partners institutional approach to research income	

Leader	Strategic Planning and Institutional Research
Contributors	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact; Research Office; Action Plan Taskforce; CATALISI/Other Networks/Partners
Start date	Mar-24
End date	Dec-24
Milestones	June identify key cases to explore
Resources	Desk research; acceleration services; meetings/exchanges
Obstacles	Identifying which models we can learn most from, have best applicability for UCC
Mitigation measures	First milestone to identify key cases will consider a 'long list' of options and devise rationale for selected cases
KPIs	Develop 3 x international case examples
Baseline value	0
Target value	3
Activity: Scope and Brief for co-design co-design and pilot actions and initiatives that inform how the insitutional can realise greater balance and diversification of research income..	
Leader	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact
Contributors	Research Office; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Action Plan Taskforce + Key Internal Stakeholders
Start date	Nov-24
End date	Mar-25
Milestones	Jan 25 gather inputs from contributors
Resources	Desktop, meetings and co-creation skills/interaction design expertise
Obstacles	Poorly devised scope and brief will reduce potential for co-designing activities.
Mitigation measures	Development work with AP Taskforce; interation design expertise and Research Office to for a clear 'Co-Design' Brief and co-design process
KPIs	Co-design scope and brief
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Co-design pilot new income model actions and initiatives that inform how the insitutional can realise greater balance and diversification of research income	
Leader	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact

Contributors	Research Office; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Action Plan Taskforce + Living Lab stakeholders
Start date	Apr-25
End date	Sep-25
Milestones	Co-creation workshop - May 25
Resources	Desktop, meetings and co-creation skills/interaction design expertise
Obstacles	Ensuring mechanisms in place for practical application/implementation of potential pilot actions
Mitigation measures	Preparatory work to secure support for practical implementation.
KPIs	Co-creation event
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Culture and Communications - Launch pilot action(s)	
Leader	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact
Contributors	Research Office; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Comms;
Start date	Dec-24
End date	Dec-25
Milestones	Launch pilot Sept 25
Resources	Content and pilot development post co-design workshop
Obstacles	Not embedded in the wider strategic planning of the University
Mitigation measures	Identify comms action to build leadership awareness and commitment
KPIs	Launch of pilot action(s) - associated news/notice for dissemination
Baseline value	0
Target value	1

Intervention Area: Sustainability of Research Finance

Goal: Research Culture: Communications

Activity: Develop Communication and Dissemination Plan to support Action Plan Goals	
Leader	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact
Contributors	Research Office; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Comms;
Start date	Mar-24
End date	UCC Action Plan Communication and Dissemination Plan
Milestones	Coordination and comms inputs from Action Plan leads
Resources	Achieving visibility with key stakeholders
Obstacles	Focus on strategic key moments and tools for comms/dissemination
Mitigation measures	Communication Plan
KPIs	Current State Overview Report
Baseline value	0
Target value	1
Activity: Culture and Communications - Disseminate co-designed model - see Goal 3	
Leader	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact
Contributors	Research Office; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Comms;
Start date	Dec-24
End date	Dec-25
Milestones	
Resources	
Obstacles	
Mitigation measures	
KPIs	
Baseline value	
Target value	
Activity: Culture and Communications - Launch ER Model - see goal 4	

Leader	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact
Contributors	Research Office; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Comms;
Start date	Dec-24
End date	Dec-25
Milestones	
Resources	
Obstacles	
Mitigation measures	
KPIs	
Baseline value	
Target value	
Activity: Culture and Communications - Launch new income pilot actions - see goal 5	
Leader	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact
Contributors	Research Office; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Comms;
Start date	Dec-24
End date	Dec-25
Milestones	
Resources	
Obstacles	
Mitigation measures	
KPIs	
Baseline value	
Target value	
Activity: Communications to support Research Culture - Develop key comms tools and identify key platforms/fora/activities to present and promote CATALISI and transformation goal/activity to build awareness of the issues and activities and support engagement and influence for transformation	
Leader	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact
Contributors	Research Office; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Comms;
Start date	Dec-24

End date	Dec-25
Milestones	UCC Action Plan Communication and Dissemination Plan - identifying key comms actions / tools/platforms
Resources	Coordination and comms inputs from Action Plan leads
Obstacles	Achieving visibility with key stakeholders
Mitigation measures	Focus on strategic key moments and tools for comms/dissemination aligned to outcomes of goals.
KPIs	Communications outputs (presentations, workvivo/news articles, leaflets etc)
Baseline value	0
Target value	5
Activity: Coordinate and monitor ongoing communications activities and outputs	
Leader	Research Culture, Engagement and Impact
Contributors	Research Office; Strategic Planning and Institutional Research; Comms;
Start date	Dec-24
End date	Dec-25
Milestones	Annual Action Plan review and update
Resources	Communications oversight and coordination
Obstacles	Ensuring clarity/visibility of all comms as CATALISI and joined-up picture
Mitigation measures	Keep CATALISI pages on website up to date with overall vision of AP activities
KPIs	Communication Report
Baseline value	0
Target value	1

ANNEX 10 – UG ACTION PLAN

Intervention Area: Public engagement with and outreach to society to solve social challenges

GOAL: Establishment of a Strategic Team for seaports

Activity: Establishment of the Project Team	
Leader	Monika Adamczuk
Contributors	Julian Wierciński, Sebastian Susmarski, Katarzyna Gronowska, Mariusz Makowski, Dorota Pyć, Agata Rudnik, Krzysztof Szczepaniak
Start date	05/03/2024
End date	12/03/2024
Milestones	Kick-off meeting
Resources	Internet, computer, e-mail, phone, MS Teams
Obstacles	Problems with organizing the meeting due to work commitments (contributors=directors of university-wide units);
Mitigation measures	Scheduling a kick-off meeting well in advance Development of an action plan
KPIs	Development of an action plan
Baseline value	1
Target value	1
Activity: Preparation of a social media information and communication campaign	
Leader	Monika Adamczuk
Contributors	Szymon Gronowski
Start date	20/03/2024
End date	30/04/2024
Milestones	Launch of outreach campaign on UG's LinkedIn portal
Resources	Internet, computer, e-mail, phone, MS Teams
Obstacles	Difficulties in contacting the UG Press Team and the Promotion Office responsible for the UG LinkedIn portal
Mitigation measures	Develop rules of cooperation between the UG Cooperation and Development Office and the Press Team and the Promotion Team regarding the use of and access to the rights of the University of Gdansk's LinkedIn account
KPIs	Conception of an information and communication campaign
Baseline value	1
Target value	1
Activity: Implementation of the information and communication campaign	

Leader	Monika Adamczuk
Contributors	Szymon Gronowski, Wojciech Głodek
Start date	06/05/2024
End date	31/12/2025
Milestones	Information and communication campaign
Resources	Internet, computer, e-mail, phone, MS Teams, Camera, office suppliers
Obstacles	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Problems preparing content for LinkedIn posts due to work commitments 2. Low interest in the information and communication campaign
Mitigation measures	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Planning activities well in advance 2. Designating other employees to prepare content for posts on the University of Gdańsk's LinkedIn portal 3. Taking care of the most innovative and creative content possible. Modifying the content of messages/posts to make them more attractive to the socio-economic environment
KPIs	Report on the implementation of the information and communication campaign
Baseline value	1
Target value	1
Activity: Organising an intellectual property week event	
Leader	Sylwia Mrozowska
Contributors	Katarzyna Gronowska
Start date	22/04/2024
End date	26/04/2024
Milestones	Event Intellectual Property Week
Resources	Internet, Computer, e-mail, phone, MS Teams, Camera, office suppliers, premises, projectors
Obstacles	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Low interest in the event 2. Unable to hire rooms due to teaching loads
Mitigation measures	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Disseminating information about the event on the UG, Technology Transfer Office and UG faculties' websites, as well as on social media - UG facebook and UG LinkedIn 2. Booking the rooms well in advance
KPIs	Implementation of the event according to the planned agenda

Baseline value	1
Target value	1
Activity: Training for UG staff and entrepreneurs in preparing project applications for competitions in which consortia consisting of HEI and enterprises are eligible	
Leader	Monika Adamczuk
Contributors	Julian Wierciński, Ewa Weronis
Start date	06/05/2024
End date	31/12/2025
Milestones	Training for UG staff and entrepreneurs interested in submitting joint project proposals
Resources	Internet, computer, e-mail, phone, MS Teams, camera, offices suppliers, premises, projectors
Obstacles	Problems in recruiting participants
Mitigation measures	1. Dissemination of training information on the UG website and project website https://projekty.ug.edu.pl/ , staff newsletter 2. Sending personal invitations to participants
KPIs	Number of trainings carried out
Baseline value	3
Target value	3

Intervention Area: Public engagement with and outreach to society to solve social challenges
GOAL: Preparation of dedicated bachelor's and master's theses for business

Activity: Business sends to Faculty thesis topics	
Leader	Przemysław Borkowski
Contributors	Dariusz Tłoczyński Agnieszka Szmelter-Jarosz
Start date	01/05/2024
End date	9/30/2024
Milestones	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Preparation of topics for discussions with companies 2. Preparation of letter of intent for cooperation 3. Conduct interviews with entrepreneurs
Resources	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. E-mail 2. Computer 3. Paper
Obstacles	Reluctance of companies to talk to the University
Mitigation measures	Building on existing relationships with the business
KPIs	Number of inquiries sent to companies
Baseline value	10
Target value	20
Activity: Distribution of thesis title sat the Economic Faculty (promoters and students)	
Leader	Przemysław Borkowski
Contributors	Dariusz Tłoczyński Agnieszka Szmelter-Jarosz
Start date	01.10.2024
End date	31.10.2024
Milestones	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Selection of thesis supervisors 2. Selection of students
Resources	E-mail Computer Paper
Obstacles	Reluctance of potential promoters to work with business Lack of students capable of responding to the needs of business
Mitigation measures	Prior assessment of student potential Selection of tutors with experience in working with companies on the project
KPIs	number of works to be carried out
Baseline value	5
Target value	10

Activity: Thesis preparation	
Leader	Przemysław Borkowski
Contributors	Dariusz Tłoczyński Agnieszka Szmelter-Jarosz
Start date	01.11.2024
End date	30.07.2025
Milestones	Preparation of a work plan Preparation of the aim of the work Identify and find a bibliography Writing up the chapters of the thesis Writing the introduction and conclusion Revision of the thesis Preparation of the bibliography
Resources	E-mail Computer Paper
Obstacles	Lack of progress by the student lack of understanding of the needs of the company student illness interrupting the course of work
Mitigation measures	A supportive role for the promoter, who has experience in promoting work of an applied nature support from other Faculty members
KPIs	Number of pages written per month
Baseline value	2
Target value	5
Activity: Consultation with the Company	
Leader	Przemysław Borkowski
Contributors	Dariusz Tłoczyński Agnieszka Szmelter-Jarosz
Start date	01.02.2025
End date	7/30/2025
Milestones	Online or in-person meetings with a company representative
Resources	E-mail computer MS Teams
Obstacles	Lack of understanding between the company and the student and the supervisor
Mitigation measures	Development of a code of good practice for effective communication with the business
KPIs	Number of meetings with entrepreneurs
Baseline value	1
Target value	5

Activity: Defense of the thesis	
Leader	Przemysław Borkowski
Contributors	Dariusz Tłoczyński Agnieszka Szmelter-jarosz
Start date	01.06.2025
End date	30.07.2025
Milestones	Official thesis defense
Resources	E-mail Computer
Obstacles	Absence of the student for health reasons
Mitigation measures	Planning of possible additional dates
KPIs	Number of theses defenses
Baseline value	4
Target value	10
Activity: Submission of the thesis to the business	
Leader	Przemysław borkowski
Contributors	Dariusz tłoczyński Agnieszka szmelter-jarosz
Start date	01.06.2025
End date	12.31.2025
Milestones	1. Handing over the work to the company representatives 2. Student meets with company representative and discusses work
Resources	E-mail Computer
Obstacles	Failure of the student to deliver the agreed result difficulties of the student to provide information
Mitigation measures	Constant supervision of the student's work by the supervisor practice with the student the presentation for the enterprise
KPIs	Number of works presented
Baseline value	3
Target value	10

Intervention Area: Recognition of qualifications & research careers
GOAL: Week of current knowledge

Activity: Form a Planning Committee	
Leader	Joanna Czerepko
Contributors	Dariusz Tłoczyński; Przemysław Borkowski; Agnieszka Szmelter-Jarosz; Katarzyna Osiecka-Brzeska
Start date	5/2/2024
End date	5/12/2024
Milestones	1. Initial meeting 2. Choosing a waste paper collector
Resources	Internet computer e-mail phone MS Teams
Obstacles	1. Selection of an incompetent operator 2. Difficulties in holding organizational of meetings due to teaching loads
Mitigation measures	1. Carry out a market analysis and obtain opinions from, among others, the internet 2. Interviews with several selected collectors
KPIs	Contract with chosen waste paper collector
Baseline value	1
Target value	1
Activity: Information campaign	
Leader	Joanna Czerepko
Contributors	Dariusz Tłoczyński; Przemysław Borkowski; Agnieszka Szmelter-Jarosz; Katarzyna Osiecka-Brzeska
Start date	5/13/2024
End date	6/9/2024
Milestones	Information on the website of the Faculty of Economics and the Faculty of Management
Resources	Internet, computer, e-mail, phone, MS Teams
Obstacles	1. Low interest of message recipients 2. Unattractive or unclear messages
Mitigation measures	1. Exposure to content for more than 3 weeks 2. Consultation of the content of the message with team members
KPIs	1. Number of communications posted 2. Number of posters printed and pasted
Baseline value	1. (2) 2. (4)

Target value	1. (4) 2. (6)
Activity: Week of current knowledge - pilot	
Leader	Joanna Czerepko
Contributors	Dariusz Tłoczyński; Przemysław Borkowski; Agnieszka Szmelter-Jarosz; Katarzyna Osiecka-Brzeska
Start date	6/10/2024
End date	6/14/2024
Milestones	Conducting collections at points in the Faculty of Economics and Faculty of Management
Resources	Demarcated physical collection points (and possibly cardboard boxes)
Obstacles	1. Low interest rate 2. The need to protect personal data in the case of theses 3. Necessity to keep the theses under regulations
Mitigation measures	1. Carry out promotional activities in advance 2. Use of personal contacts and relationships
KPIs	Waste paper collected in kilograms
Baseline value	50
Target value	150
Activity: Summary of action	
Leader	Joanna Czerepko
Contributors	Dariusz Tłoczyński; Przemysław Borkowski; Agnieszka Szmelter-Jarosz; Katarzyna Osiecka-Brzeska
Start date	6/15/2024
End date	6/21/2024
Milestones	Preparation of a summary report including a description of the action carried out, an assessment of the risks and conclusions for the future
Resources	Internet, computer, e-mail, phone, MS Teams
Obstacles	Lack of material to create a report
Mitigation measures	Taking notes and photos during the collection week
KPIs	Report - summary (pages)
Baseline value	3
Target value	5

Intervention Area: Sustainability in campus operation
GOAL: ECOthon - close the loop

Activity: Define the Scope and Guidelines	
Leader	Joanna Czerepko
Contributors	Dariusz Tłoczyński; Przemysław Borkowski; Agnieszka Szmelter-Jarosz; Katarzyna Osiecka-Brzeska; Magdalena Markiewicz
Start date	1/2/2025
End date	1/31/2025
Milestones	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Initial meeting 2. Set up project goals and scope 3. Obtaining approvals for the event
Resources	Internet, computer, e-mail, phon, MS Teams
Obstacles	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The problem of obtaining consents to organise an event 2. Difficulties in holding organisationof all meetings due to teaching loads
Mitigation measures	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Carry out a market analysis and obtain opinions from, among others, the internet 2. Start the consent process at the very beginning
KPIs	Official agreement on the preparation of the event
Baseline value	1
Target value	1
Activity: Create a Promotion Plan	
Leader	Joanna Czerepko
Contributors	Dariusz Tłoczyński; Przemysław Borkowski; Agnieszka Szmelter-Jarosz; Katarzyna Osiecka-Brzeska; Magdalena Markiewicz
Start date	1/31/2025
End date	2/28/2025
Milestones	Preparation of an event promotion plan
Resources	Internet computer e-mail phone MS Teams
Obstacles	Inadequate communication, not adapted to the target group
Mitigation measures	Involvement of students in the creation of promotional activities for the project
KPIs	Promotion plan (document; pages)
Baseline value	2
Target value	5
Activity: Collaborate with Student Organizations	
Leader	Joanna Czerepko

Contributors	Dariusz Tłoczyński; Przemysław Borkowski; Agnieszka Szmelter-Jarosz; Katarzyna Osiecka-Brzeska; Magdalena Markiewicz
Start date	3/1/2025
End date	4/27/2025
Milestones	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Establishing contact with the student research clubs of the Faculty of Economics and the Faculty of Management 2. Establishing contact with other student organisations
Resources	Internet, computer, e-mail, phon, MS Teams
Obstacles	Lack of willingness to cooperate on the part of student groups
Mitigation measures	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identify in advance (for example during class) whether students are interested in the topic 2. Promotional activities already during the course
KPIs	Number of organisations contacted
Baseline value	2
Target value	5
Activity:	
Main event: closed loop run combined with world clean up (Earth Day)	
Leader	Joanna Czerepko
Contributors	Dariusz Tłoczyński; Przemysław Borkowski; Agnieszka Szmelter-Jarosz; Katarzyna Osiecka-Brzeska; Magdalena Markiewicz
Start date	4/22/2025
End date	4/22/2025
Milestones	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Preparation of the event 2. Running the race 3. Presenting gifts to the winners 4. Joint cleaning of the world in Sopot
Resources	gifts for the winners
Obstacles	Lack of interest in the event
Mitigation measures	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Carry out promotional activities among students 2. Involve students in designing the event
KPIs	Number of participants
Baseline value	10
Target value	100
Activity: Accompanying events	
Leader	Joanna Czerepko

Contributors	Dariusz Tłoczyński; Przemysław Borkowski; Agnieszka Szmelter-Jarosz; Katarzyna Osiecka-Brzeska; Magdalena Markiewicz		
Start date	4/21/2025		
End date	4/27/2025		
Milestones	1. preparation of the accompanying event		
Resources	Computer		
Obstacles	Lack of interest in the event		
Mitigation measures	1. Carry out promotional activities among students 2. Involve students in designing the event		
KPIs	Number of additional events		
Baseline value	1		
Target value	5		
Activity: Summary of action			
Leader	Joanna Czerepko		
Contributors	Dariusz Tłoczyński; Przemysław Borkowski; Agnieszka Szmelter-Jarosz; Katarzyna Osiecka-Brzeska; Magdalena Markiewicz		
Start date	4/28/2025		
End date	5/11/2025		
Milestones	Preparation of a summary report including a description of the action carried out		
Resources	Internet computer	e-mail	phone
	MS Teams		
Obstacles	Lack of material to create a report		
Mitigation measures	Taking notes and photos during the collection week		
KPIs	Report - summary (pages)		
Baseline value	3		
Target value	5		
Activity: Encourage Continued Exchanges			
Leader	Joanna Czerepko		
Contributors	Dariusz Tłoczyński; Przemysław Borkowski; Agnieszka Szmelter-Jarosz; Katarzyna Osiecka-Brzeska		
Start date	4/28/2025		
End date	5/11/2025		
Milestones	Preparation of recommendations based on the events		
Resources	Internet computer	e-mail	phone
	MS Teams		

Obstacles	Lack of material to create a report
Mitigation measures	Taking notes and photos during the collection week
KPIs	Report - recommendations (pages)
Baseline value	3
Target value	5